

TRITECH

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Hywel Dda University Health Board

High Risk CVD Project Final Report

**Next Generation Population Health:
Demonstrating a comprehensive approach to risk prediction
and prevention for cardiovascular disease (CVD) patients.**

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Who We Are

In 2021 the TriTech Institute was launched. We are a team based in a bespoke facility within the Hywel Dda University Health Board comprising of industry-leading engineers, scientists, and clinicians.

Our Institute

Here at the TriTech Institute, we support the development of healthcare solutions on a local, national, and global level offering designers and manufacturers a single point of access to the NHS through a collaborative and agile approach.

What We Offer

The team's advanced skills in clinical and research design are combined with technical engineering expertise to manage the whole innovative pathway from early unmet need, through to concept design, prototyping, clinical testing, and real-world service evaluations.

Our Services

We provide specific services and solutions for clinical engineering, research and innovation, and value-based healthcare, and can also support with grant writing and submission.

Executive Summary

Situation

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) remains a leading cause of death and ill-health in Wales (and the world), accounting for approximately 30% of all deaths, with ischaemic heart disease being the most common cause. CVD also places a significant burden on the healthcare system, contributing to 7% of all inpatient admissions and 9% of emergency admissions annually.

Despite its prevalence, atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD), the most common form of CVD, is largely preventable. Prevention efforts focus on managing modifiable risk factors, which include high blood pressure, raised cholesterol, diabetes, smoking, physical inactivity, unhealthy diet, and obesity.

Key Modifiable Risk Factors:

- Hypertension: The leading modifiable risk factor in Wales, linked to half of all heart attacks and strokes. Over 200,000 individuals may remain undiagnosed.
- Dyslipidaemia: High LDL cholesterol is a major contributor to ASCVD. Effective management includes lifestyle changes and lipid-lowering therapies such as statins and PCSK9 inhibitors.
- Diabetes Mellitus: Significantly increases ASCVD risk, especially when combined with other comorbidities. Management includes lifestyle interventions and glucose, blood pressure, and lipid control.
- Smoking: A major global contributor to CVD. Smoking cessation significantly reduces risk, even in long-term smokers.
- Obesity, Diet, and Physical Inactivity: Obesity is rising in Wales and is closely linked to other risk factors. Physical activity can reduce coronary heart disease risk by up to 30%.

Phase 1 and Phase 2

In 2022, a strategic partnership was developed between Amgen Ltd, Hywel Dda University Health Board, Swansea Bay University Health Board and Swansea University to collaborate and develop a programme to address the national CVD

prevention challenges in South and West Wales. The programme aimed to Develop a 'Learning lab' for population risk prediction and high intensity intervention in a controlled health system, targeting better outcomes. This experiment with NHS Wales, aims to develop a Learning lab' for population risk prediction and high intensity intervention in a controlled health system, targeting better outcomes. To achieve this the programme would:

• **Phase 1:** leverage the existing Data & Informatics ecosystem (SAIL database) to explore the extent of the issue of CVD in Wales and to identify patient cohorts at high risk of future disease. Partnering with NHS Wales (and other stakeholders) allows us to leverage the existing Data & Informatics ecosystem to identify patient cohorts at high risk of future disease

• **Phase 2:** Deliver, test & evaluate focused, high intensity interventions in high ASCVD patient cohorts to reduce the treatment gap & improve outcomes. To identify ways to enhance access to effective treatment for patients in selected pilot geography, with a view to scale in the future.

This approach provides an opportunity for disciplined experimentation to inform future approaches to collaboration and system value and develop deeper insight into how health systems could respond more optimally to innovative access solutions. With a hope in providing:

- Value to Patients and the Public: Improved Outcomes and patient experience / empowerment after an CVD diagnosis (leading to better outcomes/ behaviour change)
- Value to the Healthcare System: Reduce inequalities across phenotypes and localities and therefore reduce the burden of disease on the health care system, with evidence to inform future approaches to population health strategy, planning and future policy direction.
- Value to Commercial Partners: Position Amgen as a strategic partner with a national health system and facilitate the scalability of learnings across other markets in the UK as well as internationally.

Rooted in a shared commitment to innovation, equity, and evidence-based care, the programme set out to explore how data-driven insights and targeted interventions could reshape the way health systems identify and support individuals at greatest risk.

By harnessing the power of Wales' rich informatics infrastructure and fostering a culture of collaborative experimentation, the initiative has generated valuable learning on how to deliver meaningful outcomes for patients, the NHS, and industry partners alike. The following conclusions reflect on the progress made, the insights gained, and the opportunities that lie ahead.

Conclusions

Phase 1: Understanding the gap in CVD management in Wales

1. Rising Disease Burden
 - ASCVD prevalence increased from 8.9% to 9.4% (2010-22), equating to ~30,000 additional patients requiring care.
 - Diabetes Mellitus (DM) prevalence increased from 6.5% to 8.2% (2010-23) with the average age of diagnosis of diabetes decreasing.
2. Gaps in Risk Factor Management
 - The proportion patients with ASCVD prescribed lipid lowering therapy (LLT) decreased from 75.3% to 67.1%.
 - Documentation of LDL-C in this group also decreased from 58.0% to 49.3%.
 - In incident ASCVD patients only 47% achieved an LDL-C <1.8mmol/L in 2022.
 - Patients with ischaemic heart disease are more effectively managed than those with stroke and patients with PAD the least effectively managed.
3. Declining Lipid Management in DM
 - The proportion of diabetic patients (with and without established ASCVD) prescribed LLT decreased from 87.5% to 81.8% (2010-23).
 - In very high-risk diabetics without ASCVD but with chronic kidney disease the proportion prescribed LLT also decreased from 78.9% to 54.9%.
 - Considering diabetic patients without ASCVD or CKD, only 44.2% had a documented QRISK

score in 2022 and of those with a 10-year risk >20%, only half were prescribed LLT.

4. Consequences of Poor Management
 - Most patients experiencing a first MI or stroke had suboptimal lipid/BP control in the year prior, even with documented risk factors (e.g., hypertension, CKD, DM).
5. Need for Better Risk Stratification and development of a new Risk Calculator (REACT Score)
 - A secondary prevention risk calculator (e.g., REACT score) is essential to:
 - o Improve risk assessment.
 - o Support clinical decision-making.
 - o Enable high-value care for ASCVD patients.

Phase 2: Evaluating prevention themed CVD management clinics in the community

1. Clinical Effectiveness
 - The clinics demonstrated strong effectiveness in reducing LDL-C (mean reduction ~0.9–1.18 mmol/L) and systolic blood pressure (mean reduction ~16–30 mmHg).
 - 81% of patients achieved BP control (<140/90 mmHg); 37% achieved LDL-C ≤1.8 mmol/L.
 - POC lipid testing showed strong correlation with lab-based testing (Pearson r > 0.9), supporting future integration.
2. Patient Engagement
 - 69% of patients completed the full 12-month service, an encouraging retention rate for a long-term, intensive programme.
 - Patients reported feeling supported, respected, and engaged, with many crediting the service for motivating lifestyle changes and uncovering undiagnosed issues.
3. Professional Reflections
 - Staff saw the model as holistic, meaningful, and empowering for patients, but faced frustrations with governance, systems, and infrastructure.
4. Clinic Model Comparison
 - All three models (secondary care hub, community hub, GP practice) were clinically effective.

5. Cost-Effectiveness

- Model 1 (secondary care hub) yielded an ICER of £3,087/QALY, well below the NICE threshold of £20,000.
- Models 2 (community hub) and 3 (GP practice) were more costly and yielded fewer QALYs, thus were dominated in the cost-utility analysis.

6. Economic Impact

- All models showed strong lifetime value with fewer logistical costs (e.g. no staff travel) and better infrastructure support, although may not be as practical in a rural setting.
- Estimated per-patient delivery costs ranged from £438 (Model 1) to £756 (Model 3), with substantial clinical benefits in LDL-C and BP reduction.

7. Health Outcomes

- The data demonstrates that targeted intervention, by a ring-fenced resource that doesn't succumb to the acute pressures within the existing system is likely to provide significant improvement in patient outcomes.
- The programme has the potential to reduce 10-year CVD risk by ~20% through sustained lipid and BP management, potentially preventing major adverse events.

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Abbreviations

A&E	Accident and Emergency	HCP	Healthcare Professional
ABUHB	Aneurin Bevan University Health Board	HDUHB	Hywel Dda University Health Board
AI	Artificial Intelligence	IGRP	Islet-specific Glucose-6-phosphatase catalytic subunit-Related Protein
ASCVD	Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease	IHD	Ischemic Heart Disease
AWTTC	All Wales Therapeutics and Toxicology Centre	IQR	Interquartile Range
BCUHB	Betsi Cadwaladr University Health Board	LDL	Low-density lipoprotein
BP	Blood Pressure	LLT	Lipid lowering therapy
CAD	Coronary Artery Disease	NHS	National Health Service
CVUHB	Cardiff and Vale University Health Board	NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
CHD	Coronary Heart Disease	PCI	Percutaneous Coronary Intervention
CKD	Chronic Kidney Disease	PTHB	Powys Teaching Health Board
CLR	Critical Literature Review	PREM	Patient Recorded Experience Measure
CTMUHB	Cwm Taf Morgannwg University Health Board	PROM	Patient Recorded Outcome Measure
CVD	Cardiovascular Disease	R&D	Research and Development
DM	Diabetes Mellitus	RCP3Q	Royal College of Physicians 3 Questions
DHCW	Digital Health and Care Wales	SAIL	Secure Anonymised Information Linkage
DHT	Digital Health Technologies	SAMD	Software as a Medical Device
ED	Emergency Department	SBUHB	Swansea Bay University Health Board
ESC	European Cardiology Society	SCORE2	Systematic Coronary Risk Evaluation 2
GP	General Practitioner		

1 Prevention of Cardiovascular Disease in Wales: Background and Rationale for Partnership

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is a term which covers a wide range of conditions affecting the heart, blood vessels, or both. CVD is a leading cause of ill-health and death in Wales and is a priority area for the Welsh Government and NHS Wales.[1] CVD causes around 30% of all deaths in Wales where ischaemic heart disease was the leading cause of mortality in 2022 (3,922 deaths) (Deaths registered in England and Wales, 2014 - 2023, Office for National Statistics).

In addition it is approximated that around 7% of all inpatient hospital admissions in Wales are due to causes related to CVD.[2] Furthermore, there are around 33,000 emergency admissions for CVD each year, which accounts for 9% of all emergency admissions. Around a third of these admissions for CVD are for coronary heart disease (CHD), another third for other forms of heart disease and the final third for other cardiovascular conditions “beyond the heart”, most commonly stroke and peripheral arterial disease.

Whilst CVD remains a significant issue across the world and still has a significant impact on healthcare services, atherosclerotic CVD (ASCVD) the most common form of CVD can be preventable. There are many comorbidities that can increase the risk of developing ASCVD which include: hypertension, diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney disease, dyslipidaemia, rheumatoid arthritis, influenza, serious mental health problems, and periodontitis. The role of several key risk factors has been well established with each risk factor increasing a person’s likelihood of developing ASCVD.[3] Some of the risk factors cannot be controlled such as age and sex, family history of CVD, and ethnic background; but there are several others, known as modifiable risk factors, which can be controlled, treated or modified.

1.1 Modifiable Risk factors for CVD

Management of modifiable risk factors is the most effective strategy for prevention and reducing progression of ASCVD. This includes

management of high blood pressure, reduction of lipids, maintaining a healthy body mass index, diet, exercise, stopping smoking and limiting alcohol.

1.1.1 High Blood Pressure (Hypertension)

Hypertension is the leading modifiable risk for heart and circulatory diseases in Wales. It is estimated that around half of all heart attacks and strokes in Wales are associated with high blood pressure. Whilst almost 530,000 people in Wales are captured on their GP’s hypertension register, it is estimated that as over 200,000 people could be undiagnosed.[4] The primary prevention strategy for controlling risk due to high blood pressure is through lifestyle changes (– particularly diet exercise and weight loss) and prescription of antihypertensive drugs where clinically indicated.

1.1.2 Raised cholesterol (Dyslipidaemia)

High cholesterol levels (termed dyslipidaemia) is a major risk- factor for ASCVD, underpinning the development of the atherosclerotic plaques in the arteries responsible for the clinical manifestations of the disease. It is estimated that 1 in 5 deaths from heart and circulatory diseases in Wales are associated with high (low-density lipoprotein, LDL) lipids. Whilst lifestyle changes are often beneficial, the prescription of lipid lowering therapy (LLT) such as statin drugs are usually indicated for risk reduction in those patients with and at high risk of ASCVD.

Additional LLTs, including Ezetimibe and or agents interfering with PCSK9 activity are indicated in very high-risk patients for whom statin therapy is inadequate or not tolerated and where cholesterol levels remain uncontrolled.

For example, lowering raised serum (LDL) cholesterol levels reduces the relative risk of major adverse CVD events by just over 20% along with a 10% reduction in all-cause mortality per 1mmol/L reduction in LDL at any given level of absolute risk.[5]

1.1.3 Diabetes Mellitus

A person with Diabetes Mellitus (DM) has a substantially elevated risk of ASCVD, in addition the frequent presence of other risk factors such as dyslipidaemia, hypertension and CKD can significantly amplify the risk.[6] Another major issue is that following a cardiovascular event a person with DM is more likely to suffer from a poorer prognosis compared to a person without DM. To mitigate the cardiovascular risks caused by DM the best treatments are through living a healthy lifestyle and through with various medications for managing high glucose levels as well as blood pressure and cholesterol.

1.1.4 Smoking

Tobacco use is a major contributor to the risk of CVD and remains a significant public health issue[7]. The risk of developing smoking-related diseases increases with how long and how much someone has smoked. These risks fall substantially if smoking is stopped, even for long-term smokers. Therefore, promoting and supporting people to give up or reduce their smoking intake, such as enabling people

to access smoking cessation services, will significantly reduce a person's CVD risk.

1.1.5 Physical inactivity, unhealthy diet and obesity

Another key modifiable risk for CVD is obesity. Obesity is strongly associated with other risk factors such as raised blood pressure and type 2 diabetes and is associated with eating an unhealthy dietary habit, lack of physical activity and sedentary lifestyles. The best way to reduce the risks caused through obesity is to promote physical activity and diet modification, being physically active can reduce the risk of coronary heart disease by up to 30%.[8]

1.1.6 Prevalence of Modifiable Risk Factors

The prevalence of risk factors for CVD in Wales has not seen much of a reduction over the past 10 years. Despite the reduction in levels of smoking there has been a steady increase in the rates of obesity, where now a quarter of the population in Wales can be classified as obese (see Figure 1). The increase in obesity has resulted in increased risks of hypertension and high cholesterol.[1]

Figure 1. Graph showing the prevalence of modifiable risk factors of CVD in Wales, Public Health Wales Observatory, 2024.

1.2 Risk Mitigation

All patients who have had a CVD risk assessment should be given lifestyle advice, regardless of their risk score. This should include advice about:

- Smoking cessation.
- Promoting a healthy diet and regular physical activity to promote weight loss if overweight or obesity.
- Keeping alcohol consumption within the recommended limits.
- Statin treatment (+/- other lipid lowering therapies) should be offered for the primary prevention of CVD to people with an estimated 10-year CVD risk of 10% or more if lifestyle interventions have not proved effective.
- Antihypertensive medication should be used, where lifestyle measures alone are inadequate, for those with hypertension as effective control of blood pressure can have a significant impact on the risk of CVD events.

Despite the overwhelming evidence of their effectiveness, implementation of effective risk factor management regimes has proved difficult in the wider population. The high burden of morbidity and mortality from ASCVD remains a major public health issue across Wales (and worldwide), despite continued efforts to enact guidelines nationally and internationally to promote risk mitigation and improve CVD management/prevention services.

1.3 National/International Guidelines

Effective and safe risk factor treatments have been developed, and most drugs are now generic and available at low costs. Nevertheless, the prevalence of unhealthy lifestyles is still high, and risk factors for ASCVD are often inadequately managed, even in patients considered to be at high (residual) CVD risk.

Prevention of CVD events by managing modifiable risk factors is the topic of these guidelines. Relevant to UK clinical practice, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) and the European Society of Cardiology/ European Atherosclerosis Society have issued national guidance on CVD prevention.[9,10]

1.3.1 National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE): guidelines for CVD prevention and Management

NICE produced guidelines (published in 2023) on the risk assessment and reduction of CVD ([Cardiovascular disease: risk assessment and reduction, including lipid modification](#)).[11] The guidelines underline the importance of a staged, individualised approach to CVD prevention, which is underpinned by shared decision making. NICE recommend an ongoing approach to full risk assessment, based on the presence of risk factors identified through electronic health records. Established risk assessment tools, such as QRISK3 are recommended for individuals aged 25-84 who are not at increased risk of CVD due to comorbidities or family history. Those aged over 85 should be considered at high risk based on age alone. Full lipid profiles are recommended for those deemed at high risk of developing CVD.

Based on test results, primary prevention strategies should include the promotion of lifestyle factors associated with reduced CVD risk. Statins are recommended for primary prevention only if lifestyle factors have been optimised and other potential causes of dyslipidaemia have been ruled out. Secondary prevention strategies include the prescription of statins and combined lipid-lowering treatment.

Annual medication reviews are recommended for those on lipid-lowering treatment and those at high risk of CVD. Areas for research prioritisation identified by NICE include the simplification of risk assessment, statin treatment in older people, and lipid-lowering treatment for people with type 1 diabetes.

1.3.2 European Cardiology Society (ESC): Guidelines on CVD prevention and Management

Published in 2021, the ESC produced Guidelines on CVD prevention in clinical practice (<https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehab484>).[12] The guidelines aim to provide a single set of guidelines for primary and secondary care settings (Figure 2).

Figure 2. ESC guidelines for CVD prevention for primary and secondary prevention settings.

Like the NICE guidelines the ESC guidelines promote staged, individualised CVD risk prevention and centre shared decision making between patients and healthcare

providers. According to these guidelines, individuals should be risk assessed using existing algorithms, namely the SCORE2, or SCORE2-OP for people aged 70 and above.

Primary prevention strategies, which apply to those at all risk levels, include the promotion of lifestyle factors associated with reduced CVD risk e.g., smoking cessation and reduced saturated fat intake. Secondary prevention strategies for those with existing ASCVD, include the promotion of lifestyle factors alongside statin use or additional/alternative LLT.

In response to these sets of guidelines, several strategy documents, policies and legislation have been developed in Wales with the aim of addressing the prevalence of unhealthy lifestyles in Wales to reduce the prevalence of ASCVD risk factors and to address the issue of people with CVD that are poorly treated or managed.

1.4 Strategies and Legislation in Wales

Welsh government and the NHS in Wales have implemented several guidelines, strategies, policies and legislation that has been developed and published for Wales. The “Halcox Report” into vascular risk management made a number of recommendations: Firstly to prioritise delivery of effective risk management in those known to have the disease, followed by development of approaches for identification and management

of risk in deprived communities in which disease incidence is highest was published in 2010 with numerous documents published since. A timeline showing when the main guidelines and policies in the last 10 years came into effect can be seen in figure 3. A full list of the different guidelines, strategies, policy and legislation can be seen in **Appendix 1**. Whilst the different documents tackle many specific and different issues and have their own agenda and purpose there are several fundamental themes that are common throughout, which include:

- Raise awareness of healthy living.
- Shift the paradigm of care for CVD from being an intervention focused secondary care service to a community/primary care prevention focussed service.
- Signpost to existing sources of information, advice and support relating to lifestyle change.
- Develop and deliver local strategies and services to tackle underlying determinants of health inequality and risk factors for coronary heart disease and CVD.
- Target resources in population areas of high risk (high areas of deprivation for example) and areas of high impact.

1.5 Prevalence of CVD in Wales

Despite policy, the prevalence of CVD has not slowed and continues to increase (see Table 1).[3]

Table 1. Table showing the change in absolute numbers of prevalence of CVD over the period 2010 to 2024.

Measure	Condition	Count in 2009/2010	Count in 2023/2024	Percentage Increase
Cardiovascular Disease	Heart Failure	28500	42500	49%
Cardiovascular Disease	Stroke/Transient Ischaemic attack	64100	72400	13%
Clinical Risk Factor	Hypertension	478000	529300	11%
Clinical Risk Factor	Atrial Fibrillation	53400	84900	59%

As a result, the overarching goal of improving the prevention of CVD has not been successful (or as successful as hoped). Despite this, there is significant evidence of improved health outcomes for people who have developed CVD, such as an associated lower mortality and admission rate. Whilst this is the case, recent evidence (2018-2020) has shown that avoidable mortality due to circulatory disease has been increasing.[3]

1.6 Cost of CVD in Wales

Current estimations on the cost if there is a slowdown in prioritising the prevention agenda and slowing or reducing CVD in England and Wales is approximately £54 billion.[13] This incorporates many factors such as healthcare, social care and value of lost quality adjusted years of life.

In Wales, a recently published (January 2025) fact file (British Heart Foundation) [14,15,16] estimated that the total NHS Wales expenditure on CVD to be around £770million annually, with the overall burden on the Welsh economy (including premature death, long-term care, disability and informal costs) an estimated £1.6 billion annually.[14]

Furthermore, evidence indicates annually increasing costs. A key element to this is the gradual increase in cost to dispensed prescriptions for CVD related causes. This reached a peak high in 2004/2005 of £151 million before decreasing to a low of £63 million in 2014/15. However, over the last 10 years this has gradually been increasing to £103 million in 2023/24. Since 2009/10, the amount of money spent on circulation problems by NHS Wales has increased from

£459 million to £706 million in 2022/23, an increase of 54 %.[17] Of that £706 million: £118 million was spent on coronary heart disease.

- £133 million was spent on cerebrovascular disease.
- £455 million was spent on other problems of circulation, which may include expenditure linked to the above sub-categories but could not be allocated directly to them.

Of this, £564 million (80% of the total) was spent in secondary care settings with the remaining 20% spent in primary care. This shows that the vast majority of the money spent on addressing CVD is spent at the 'wrong' end of the patient's journey, where the system has failed to effectively prevent the disease. Ideally, future efforts must aim to shift this paradigm and to increase (or redirect funds) to primary care and the community to prioritise prevention for lifetime CVD management.

1.7 Next Steps for Wales

1.7.1 The Issue

Despite policies and legislation to create a healthier Wales, the prevalence of CVD has increased. Regardless of the policies and legislation, prevalence of CVD disease and associated risk factors, it is recognised there is an opportunity to make a significant difference in improving CVD outcomes,

1.7.2 The Opportunity

For over 20 years, the standard approach of developing new strategies and policy documents

and then expecting these guidelines to be effectively implemented has proven unsuccessful. The reasons for this are unclear and likely multifactorial including competing clinical priorities, without ringfencing resources and staffing for delivery of preventive care services, unclear responsibility for overseeing preventive care delivery, lack of patient education and engagement amongst others. Accordingly, this provides an important challenge and opportunity to test a different model of care.

- Cardiovascular prevention is highly effective however, late diagnosis and suboptimal treatment is common.
- Risk factors, such as obesity, physical inactivity, smoking and drinking at unsafe levels, can all be modified with a measurable beneficial impact on a person's risk of developing CVD.,
- Correct monitoring and management of patient's lipid and blood pressure levels are particularly clinically and cost effective in improving patient outcomes.
- Partnering with the Healthcare System to test strategies for identifying unmet need for risk management and delivery of appropriate interventions in specific patient cohorts with the aim of reducing care "gaps" and thus outcomes.

Whilst initial evaluations would be undertaken in defined areas and populations, in addition to the immediate uplift in access to treatment for those patients in the pilot work in West Wales this will inform approaches to scale the approach more widely across Wales and beyond.

1.7.3 Next generation population health demonstrating a comprehensive approach to risk prediction and prevention for cardiovascular disease (CVD) patients.

1.7.3.1 The Vision

In 2022, a strategic partnership was developed between the TriTech Institute, Amgen Ltd, Hywel Dda University Health Board, Swansea Bay University Health Board and Swansea University to collaborate and develop a programme to address the national CVD prevention challenges in South and West Wales. The programme aimed to:

1. Develop a 'Learning lab' for population risk prediction and high intensity intervention in a controlled health system, targeting

better outcomes. This experiment with NHS Wales, aims to develop a Learning lab' for population risk prediction and high intensity intervention in a controlled health system, targeting better outcomes.

2. Utilising the Secure Anonymised Data Linkage (SAIL) databank to explore trends in presentation of patients with or at high risk of ASCVD, and identifying gaps (and opportunities) for improved risk factor management.
3. Deliver, test & evaluate focused, high intensity interventions in patients with or at high risk of ASCVD with identified treatment gap to improve outcomes

This approach provides an opportunity for disciplined experimentation to inform future approaches to collaboration and system value and develop deeper insight into how health systems could respond more optimally to innovative access solutions, with a hope in providing:

- **Value to Patients and the Public:** Improved Outcomes and patient experience / empowerment after an CVD diagnosis (leading to better outcomes/ behaviour change)
- **Value to the Healthcare System:** Reduce inequalities across phenotypes and localities and therefore reduce the burden of disease on the health care system, with evidence to inform future approaches to population health strategy, planning and future policy direction.
- **Value to Commercial Partners:** Position Amgen as a strategic partner with a national health system and facilitate the scalability of learnings across other markets in the UK as well as internationally.

1.7.3.2 The Programme

To deliver this vision the program of work will be initially divided into two key phases

1.7.3.2.1 Phase 1: Data Analytics: Trends in Cardiovascular Disease and lipid management

The initial phase utilises the Secure Anonymised Information Linkage (SAIL) database containing anonymous healthcare records of the population of Wales. In this evaluation, the researchers identified high-risk patient cohorts (with and at increased risk of ASCVD), to evaluate and improve understanding of the current gaps in treatment compared to national guidelines. This will lead to shared understanding of the clinical and economic impact of current treatment.

This evaluation will provide an up to date and accurate picture of the current CVD prevention landscape in Wales, focusing primarily on lipid management but also on Blood Pressure. These data will be used to develop a new risk stratification tool.

1.7.3.2.1 Phase 2: Implementation and evaluation of novel high risk CVD management clinics

Using existing clinical diagnostic criteria established by the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) and the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) the researchers aim to develop an algorithm based on clinical diagnoses, laboratory results and prescribed medication to improve identification of patients at increased risk of CVD events (see figure 4).

Figure 4. Infographic of phase 1 and 2 of the next generation population health demonstrating a comprehensive approach to risk prediction and prevention for cardiovascular disease (CVD) patients.

2 Phase 1: Understanding the Gap and Data Analytics: Trends in Cardiovascular Disease and lipid management

2.1 Phase 1 Outline

2.1.1 Aims for Phase 1

The aim was to develop a shared understanding of the clinical and economic impact of current treatment. Using existing clinical diagnostic criteria established by National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE)[9] and the European Society of Cardiology (ESC)[10] the researchers aim to develop an algorithm based on clinical diagnoses, laboratory results and prescribed medication to improve identification of patients at increased risk of CVD events.

The five key aims of phase 1 will be to explore the available data informatics to better understand:

1. Trends in presentation of ACSVD to understand the current gaps.
2. Trends in testing, treatment and control of lipids/BP in ASCVD.
3. Trends in CVD risk testing and lipid management in general population.

4. To test, validate & improve identification of high-risk patient cohorts.
5. Develop/validate a CVD event risk prediction tool for in patients with established ASCVD.

2.1.2 Unique opportunity: SAIL database

The data informatics environment in Wales provides a unique opportunity to fully explore the current gap and scale of CVD disease in Wales. Phase 1 focuses on utilising this existing data informatics (SAIL database) to undertake an investigation into the trends in CVD prevention in practice, with particular focus upon management at a population level in Wales (secondary prevention and high-risk primary prevention). To access the SAIL database a request must be made which details the outline of the proposal. The application is then reviewed by the SAIL review board.

An application for this project was made in April 2022. The key milestones and Key performance indicators of phase 1 can be seen in Table 2:

Table 2. Milestones and KPIs for Phase 1 of the project.

Project Phase	Milestones	KPIs
Phase 1: Data Analytics	IGRP approval by SAIL, datasets agreed include phenotype characteristics and outcome measurements	Publications
	Appointments of Research Analyst and Clinical Academic Pharmacist roles	Development of a new risk calculator
	Phenotype cohorts identified (number of patients in each cohort quantified)	
	Gain approved access to SAIL Database	
	ID high risk patient cohorts through AI and traditional methods, understand gaps	

What is SAIL? The Secure Anonymised Information Linkage (SAIL)

SAIL Databank is a national data safe haven of de identified datasets principally about the population of Wales, made available in anonymised form to researchers across the world. It holds billions of person-based records,

which enables researchers to answer important questions for the benefit of society. Researchers can access a broad range of routinely collected data spanning up to 30 years from an entire population.

2.1.3 Data Sources for Phase 1 and Record Selection

Following application and approval to access the records held on the SAIL Databank, an in-depth analysis of the dataset was performed. An analysis period of between 2010 to 2022 was chosen and the data collected would explore CVD risk prediction and prevention, and further describes individuals who utilise services in Wales, and are patients with or at high risk of coronary artery disease (CAD). To understand the extent of the problem in Wales we included:

- i. those with established CAD, who have undergone Primary coronary intervention (PCI), or diagnosis of MI/angina, and with residual CVD risk.
- ii. patients at high risk of developing CAD i.e. not had an event yet but at high risk as determined by risk factors including diabetes, hypertension, lipid levels (plus other comorbidities) - describe their existing risk (using QRISK algorithm) and opportunity for reducing CVD risk.

Several datasets in the Secure Anonymised Information Linkage (SAIL) Databank were linked including the:

- Patient Episode Database for Wales (PEDW), which records hospital admission and discharge dates, diagnoses and operational procedures, demographic data, and death date if relevant for the population of Wales
- Welsh Longitudinal General Practice (WLGP) dataset containing demographic, clinical, and prescribing data for about 85% of primary care practices across Wales
- Welsh Demographic Service Dataset (WDS), which contains basic demographic information and history of individuals' residence in Wales and registration with GP practices
- Welsh Index of Multiple Deprivation (WIMD) 2019, an area-based deprivation measure.

2.1.3.1 Full list of the data sources

The data sources included:

- Annual District Death Extract (ADDE),
- Emergency Department Dataset (EDDS),
- Outpatient Database for Wales (OPDW),

- Patient Episode Database for Wales (PEDW),
- Welsh Demographic Service Dataset (WDS),
- Welsh Longitudinal General Practice (WLGP) and
- Wales Results Reporting Service (WRRS).

2.1.3.2 Project Duration

Phase 1 began in April 2023 and ended in April 2025.

2.2 Findings for Phase 1

2.2.1 Overview of Findings

Following data collection patient records for all of Wales from the SAIL database were used. The key output for the project involves the production of 5 key peer reviewed publications taken from the data collected aimed at answering the 5 key aims for phase 1.

To address aim 1 (*Trends in presentation of ACSVD to understand the current gaps*) & 2 (*Trends in testing, treatment and control of lipids/BP in ASCVD*) two publications have been produced. One has been published and one is currently under development:

1. **Paper 1 - Trends in atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease and lipid management: a population-level observational cohort study in Wales.** (*this paper has been Published*) [*European Journal of Preventative Cardiology 2024*] 00, 1–12[18]
2. **Paper 2 - Trends in atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease and blood pressure management: a population-level observational cohort study in Wales.** (Manuscript Under development)

To address aim 3 (Trends in CVD risk testing and lipid management in general population.) a third publication has been completed and is currently under review.

3. **Paper 3 - Trends in Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease and lipid management. A population-level observational cohort study in Wales.** (*Currently in review with European Heart Journal*)

Finally, to address aim 4 (To test, validate & improve identification of high-risk patient cohorts) and aim 5 (Develop/validate a CVD event risk prediction tool for in patients with established ASCVD) two further publications are currently under development:

4. **Paper 4 - Risk factor management prior to major adverse events at first presentation of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. A population-level observational cohort study in Wales.** (Manuscript Under development)
5. **Paper 5 - Predicting risk of recurrent atherosclerotic cardiovascular events using routinely collected health characteristics in patients with established disease: derivation and validation of the REACT score -** (Manuscript Under development – confidential)

The following section provides an expanded summary of five pivotal publications that have significantly contributed to the evidence base and strategic direction for the identification, management, and treatment of high-risk and very high-risk ASCVD patients.

2.2.2 Paper 1. Trends in atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease and lipid management: a population-level observational cohort study in Wales

Published: *European Journal of Preventative Cardiology* 2024) 00, 1–12 <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurjpc/zwae233>

2.2.2.1 Aims

European clinical guidelines recommend that patients with atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD), including ischaemic heart disease (IHD), stroke and peripheral arterial disease (PAD), are prescribed lipid lowering treatment (LLT) and treated to target low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) levels.

The aim of this study was to use routinely collected linked community and hospital health data to document population-scale trends in

- i. the incidence and prevalence of ASCVD, including coronary, cerebrovascular, peripheral vascular and poly-vascular disease subgroups,
- ii. prescription of LLT,
- iii. monitoring of lipid levels, and

- iv. achievement of the European Society of Cardiology and the European Atherosclerosis Society (ESC/EAS) recommended LDL-C targets in the population of Wales, UK since 2010.

2.2.2.2 Method

A retrospective observational population study using linked health-care data (2010-22).

2.2.2.3 Results

Over the study period the number of patients with ASCVD increased from 181,153 to 207,747 (8882 to 9398 per 100,000) (Figure 5). The proportion of patients prescribed LLT decreased from 75.3% in 2010 to 67.1% in 2022; high-intensity statin therapy increased from 9.4% to 25.2% and non-high-intensity statin therapy decreased from 59.6% to 38.2% (figure 6).

The prescribing of high-intensity statin therapy was consistently higher amongst patients with IHD (10.9% in 2010 increasing to 28.0% in 2022) than in patients with stroke (4.7% to 21.6%) or PAD (3.9% to 10.6%).

The proportion of cases with documented LDL-C decreased from 58.0% in 2010 to 49.3% in 2022 (Figure 7). Of those with documented LDL-C in 2022, 44.0% achieved LDL-C <1.8 mmol/L, including 45.2% of those with IHD, 42.0% of those with stroke and only 32.8% of those with PAD (Figure 8).

Prescribing of LLT, including HI-statin therapy, documentation of LDL-C and achievement of target LDL-C levels was relatively low, especially in PAD patients. Although target achievement in "tested patients" increased over time, the proportion of patients undergoing lipid testing declined. More rigorous lipid management requires prioritisation, especially for PAD and stroke patients.

Figure 6. Prescribed lipid lowering treatment in prevalent and incident cases in the whole ASCVD population and according to the vascular disease territory (during the first and last years of study where 1 year of complete follow-up data was available).

Figure 5. Prevalence and incidence of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease according to vascular disease territory. Prevalence (top) and incidence bottom (from 2010 to 2022). Absolute numbers (left) and per 100 K of the population (right).

Figure 7. Proportion of prevalent and incident patients with a documented LDL-C test by vascular disease territory and year.

Figure 8. Lowest LDL-C for prevalent cases in 2010 and 2022 and incident cases in 2010 and 2021 by vascular disease territory.

2.2.3 Paper 2. Trends in atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease and blood pressure management: a population-level observational cohort study in Wales

(Manuscript in preparation)

2.2.3.1 Aims

In patients with established atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD), blood pressure (BP) lowering with antihypertensive therapy (AHT) improves clinical outcomes¹ Routine testing of BP with a view to treating and controlling hypertension in patients with ASCVD is well established, supported by clinical trial evidence and recommended in major national and international clinical guidelines.

The aim of this study was to use routinely collected linked primary care and hospital

healthcare data to document population-scale trends in the testing, control and treatment of blood pressure amongst patients with ASCVD, including coronary, cerebro-, and peripheral and poly-vascular disease subgroups, in the population of Wales, UK since 2010.

2.2.3.2 Method

A retrospective observational population study using linked health-care data (2010-22).

2.2.3.3 Results

Initial results show a decline in BP documentation in the year following the index ASCVD diagnosis (figure 9), and little difference in the prescribing of antihypertensive medication between those controlled and not controlled (figure 10).

Figure 9. Blood pressure assessment within one year of index ASCVD diagnosis.

Figure 10. Number of antihypertensive classes prescribed 90 days prior to the lowest documented blood pressure (and in the first 90 days in those where BP was not documented).

2.2.4 Paper 3. Trends in Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease and lipid management in patients with Diabetes Mellitus. A population-level observational cohort study in Wales. (Data presented at American Heart Association Scientific Sessions, Chicago 2024. Manuscript in review with European Heart Journal)

An abstract of this work has been presented at the American Heart Association Scientific session 2024. Circulation, Volume: 150, Issue: Suppl.1.

This paper has been accepted for publication in European Heart Journal open. DOI: [10.1093/ehjopen/oeaf158](https://doi.org/10.1093/ehjopen/oeaf158)

2.2.4.1 Aims

In patients with diabetes mellitus (DM) with atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD), or without ASCVD (secondary prevention), the prescribing of lipid lowering therapy (LLT) is an established treatment strategy endorsed by clinical guidelines. This study aimed to document (i) trends in presentation of DM, (ii) treatment, monitoring and achievement of target low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) in DM with ASCVD, and (iii) ASCVD risk assessment and lipid treatment according to risk in the DM primary prevention setting.

2.2.4.2 Method

A retrospective observational population study including 282,581 DM patients using linked health-care data (2010-23) in Wales.

2.2.4.3 Results

The prevalence of DM increased from 133,439 to 183,948 (6,504 to 8,200 per 100,000) (figure 11). The proportion of prevalent patients with established ASCVD prescribed LLT decreased from 87.5% to 81.8% (2010-23) (figure 12), testing of LDL-C decreased from 70.3% to 67.1%, and of those with documented lipids 41.0% achieved an LDL-C <1.8 mmol/L in 2010 increasing to 52.2% in 2023.

Amongst DM without ASCVD, the proportion prescribed LLT decreased from 78.9% to 54.9% in those chronic kidney disease (CKD) and from 70.7% to 55.6% in those without CKD (figure 13). Considering DM without ASCVD or CKD (LLT is recommended according to 10-year CVD risk), only 44.2% of incident DM had a documented QRISK score in 2022 and of those with a 10-year risk >20%, only half were prescribed LLT.

Increasing incidence and prevalence of DM, together with decreasing quality of risk factor management has the potential to lead to poorer health outcomes in the population if not addressed more effectively.

Figure 11. Prevalence and incidence of diabetes mellitus in patients with and without atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. Prevalence (top) and incidence bottom from 2010 to 2023. Absolute numbers (left) and per 100K of the population (right).

Figure 12. Lipid lowering treatment (A) and LDL-C testing and control (B) in prevalent cases and incident cases with established ASCVD during each year of the study period.

Figure 13. Lipid lowering treatment in prevalent cases and incident cases with chronic kidney disease (stage 3+) but without ASCVD during each year of the study period.

2.2.5 Paper 4. Risk factor management prior to major adverse events at first presentation of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. A population-level observational cohort study in Wales

Data processing for this manuscript is now complete and a manuscript is being drafted:

2.2.5.1 Background:

Atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD) often manifests initially with a fatal or non-fatal myocardial infarction or stroke often in patients not previously considered to be at increased risk. While the aetiology of atherosclerosis is well defined and the considerable benefits of risk factor (lipids and blood pressure) management in those at increased risk is well established, less is known about the effectiveness of ASCVD risk assessment and management in the period leading up to such events. A better understanding of how comprehensively identification of risk status was established and how effectively BP and lipids (where indicated) were managed in the period leading up to a first ASCVD presentation as a fatal or non-fatal MI or stroke in the population.

This novel approach to evaluating primary prevention will provide insight not only into the nature of risk assessment and impact of suboptimal preventive management, but also stimulate new ways to think about how to mitigate against devastating, often unexpected and largely preventable ASCVD events through improved primary prevention care pathways.

2.2.5.2 Aims:

This study aimed to

- Identify patients with either a fatal or non-fatal major coronary or cerebrovascular event as their first clinical presentation of ASCVD between 2010-23 and
- Assess identification of ASCVD risk and management of modifiable risk factors in the year preceding the event in these patients who died or suffered a lasting change in their health status.

2.2.5.3 Results:

We identified 227,659 patients with a first incident diagnosis of coronary or cerebrovascular ASCVD during the study period (2010-23)

102,148 presented initially with fatal or non-fatal major coronary or cerebrovascular events. These included 32,335 non-fatal MI and 24,439 fatal ischaemic coronary events and 40,955 non-fatal and 4,419 fatal strokes. A total of 60,745 (59.5%) of these patients had clinical documentation of one or more major ASCVD risk factor (MRF) documented in their clinical record prior to the index event (hypertension, CKD, Diabetes Mellitus [DM]).

Amongst patients known to have one or more of these 'MRF's, documentation of LDL-C was greater than those without a documented MRF, increasing from 38.4% to 48.1% between 2010-23 in those with MRF, compared to 15.6% to 23.3% in those without (Figure 14). Achievement of LDL-C <1.8 mmol/L

increased from 7.5% to 13.9% among the 60,745 patients with a MRF, and from only 1.0% to 2.4% of the 41,403 patients without documented MRF.

Documentation of a BP reading fell between 2010-23 for the general cohort, from 55.2% to 49.8% overall; from 68.3% to 59.9% for those with known MRF, and from 40.1% to 33.9% for those without (figure 15).

Notably, achievement of systolic and diastolic blood pressure <140 & 90, increased overall in those with BP results, but only from 26.5% in 2010 to 27.4% in 2023.

Documented achievement of target BP among the MRF group increased from 32.2% to 32.7% but fell among those without documented 'MRF' from 19.9% to 19.0%.

Figure 14. Lipid lowering treatment (A) and LDL-C testing and control (B) in the year prior to presentation, by major risk factor diagnosis.

Figure 15. Documentation and control of blood pressure in the year prior to presentation, by major risk factor diagnosis.

2.2.6 Paper 5. Predicting risk of recurrent atherosclerotic cardiovascular events using routinely collected health characteristics in patients with established disease: derivation and validation of the REACT score

(Manuscript being finalised for submission)

2.2.6.1 Aim:

To design a risk-prediction model for recurrent cardiac events in patients with established atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease, using demographic and modifiable risk characteristics, to identify those who face greatest risk and can subsequently be targeted for effective treatment strategies with a greater degree of accuracy compared to treatment thresholds defined by current guidelines for the secondary prevention population.

2.2.6.2 Method

Acknowledging the Markov assumption, we designed a model framework that incorporated two entry points dependent on the nature of first presentation of ASCVD and therefore modelled recurrent ASCVD risk separately dependent on the severity of disease at presentation.

Figure 16. Model diagram for the multi-state Markov model describing risk of recurrent atherosclerotic cardiovascular events from stable (A) and MACE (B) index diagnoses.

Namely, the model framework describes the progression of ASCVD from stable diagnosis (A) through four states: from initial diagnosis, through the first Major adverse cardiovascular

events (MACE), recurrent MACE, to death as a competing and absorbing state (Figure 16).

The model framework also describes the progression of ASCVD from presenting with a MACE (B) through 3 states: from the first MACE event, through recurrent MACE, to death as a competing and absorbing state.

2.2.6.3 Sensitivity analyses

Ad-hoc analyses were explored during model derivation to ensure the validity and accuracy of the REACT score as a tool to inform decision-making in a clinical context.

Key factors that influenced decisions on model type, structure and covariate selection included; event-rate following diagnosis and distribution of time between events; confounding among available covariates such as presence of diabetes, chronic kidney disease and respiratory disease with measured HbA1c, eGFR and current smoking status, respectively; influence of prior treatment-decision for lipids and blood pressure on measured levels.

2.2.6.4 Performance of risk prediction

Prior to model fitting, data were split into training and test sets (ratio 70:30) to allow evaluation of predictive performance. Model-predicted prevalence of each state over the follow-up period was plotted against the observed state prevalence (calculated using the Aalen-Johansen estimator) to derive a visual goodness-of-fit measure for the model.

Patient-specific passage probabilities for each state were calculated according to available follow-up and used to calculate the predicted recurrent event rate among the study population.

Using the predicted event rate, a predicted-observed plot was constructed according to risk decile and used to verify the risk-specific agreement between predicted and observed events.

The risk of recurrent atherosclerotic cardiovascular events (REACT) score be calculated as a clinical decision-making tool using the covariate profile described in the current study, for patients with established ASCVD.

2.2.6.5 Results and Conclusions

2.2.6.5.1 Patients and Events

A total of 133,727 patients were included in model development, of whom 97,804 (73.1%) patients entered with a stable diagnosis, and 35,919 (26.9%) with a MACE.

A greater proportion of patients who entered with a MACE were male, aged ≥ 80 , presented with a stroke, and actively smoked, whereas a smaller proportion had other prior comorbidities, and presented with IHD or PAD.

Of the 97,804 patients who entered with a soft diagnosis, 16,380 (16.7%) experienced a first MACE and 20,205 (20.7%) died within the follow-up period (Figure 17).

Among those 35,919 patients who entered with a first MACE, 13,004 (36.2%) experienced a recurrent event and 6,531 (18.1%) died during follow-up.

A total of 77,603 patients experienced no further event following entry to the study and were censored at the end of the follow-up period.

Figure 17. Observed transitions following each ASCVD presentation type.

2.2.6.5.2 Prognostic Markers

Different levels of risk were noted according to the nature of presentation with ASCVD in a “stable” vs “unstable” disease state.

2.2.6.5.3 Stable Presentation

Factors independently associated with greater risk of a recurrent event following “stable” diagnosis of ASCVD were aged <50 and 80-84 (compared to those aged 60-69), male sex (compared to females), index diagnosis of stroke or PAD (compared to IHD), history of smoking, comorbidities including heart failure, hypertension, dementia and diabetes, non-HDL >4.3 mmol/L (compared to ≤4.3) and eGFR 30-60 and <30 mL/min/1.73m² (compared to >60).

Factors associated with lower risk of recurrent events following diagnosis included WIMD quintile 5 (i.e., least deprived; compared to most deprived in quintile 1).

2.2.6.5.4 Unstable Presentation (Major Adverse Cardiovascular Event [MACE])

For patients presenting with a MACE, factors independently associated with greater risk of a recurrent event included ages <50 and 80-84 (compared to those aged 60-69), male sex (compared to females), index diagnosis of stroke or PAD (compared to IHD), comorbidities including heart failure, hypertension and diabetes, non-HDL >4.3 mmol/L (compared to ≤4.3) and eGFR <30 mL/min/1.73m² (compared to >60; Figure 3).

Factors associated with lower risk of recurrent events following diagnosis included WIMD quintile 2, 3 and 5 (compared to most deprived in quintile 1).

When predicting the five-year risk of a recurrent atherosclerotic cardiovascular event, there was a high level of agreement between the predicted and observed risk among all patients included in the study, following an inverse sigmoid distribution across deciles (Figure 18).

Examples include the QRISK (UK) and SCORE (Europe) family of models and the pooled cohort and Framingham risk scores (US).

However, at present, no models for risk prediction (and thus informing treatment selection according to level of risk) have been developed or clinically validated for application in a general secondary prevention ASCVD population.

Such a model should be of particular relevance to inform clinicians and payers more precisely of the expected potential clinical benefits in an individual patient and, hence, cost effectiveness at a population level for any intervention that has an (evidence-based) expected impact on clinical outcomes for any given absolute level of risk.

For example, since we know that the relative risk of major ASCVD events is likely to be 21% lower and the relative risk of death 10% lower per 1mmol/L reduction in LDL-cholesterol achieved by initiation/escalation of LLT; it follows that the higher the **absolute** risk of ASCVD events and death for any given patient, the greater the **absolute** reduction in this risk per 1 mmol/L and therefore the greater cost-effectiveness and value of escalation of therapy will be for patients at higher risk.

At present NICE treatment recommendations for escalation of LLT beyond statin therapy e.g. with PCSK9 inhibiting therapies are based on LDL-C level thresholds in the context of specific clinical scenarios (familial hypercholesterolaemia and or established/progressive ASCVD), which provide some information regarding absolute level of risk, but may leave some of the highest risk patients without access to clinically (and also potentially cost effective - given these patients very high absolute risk) treatments if their LDL-C levels are below the NICE-endorsed treatment threshold.

We have developed a model by evaluating outcomes in the population with ASCVD in the SAIL databank, which we have called the REACT score.

The model uses demographic and modifiable risk characteristics, to estimate the risk of major ASCVD events and death, in order to identify those who face greatest risk and can thus be targeted for escalation of treatment with a greater degree of accuracy compared to

treatment thresholds defined by current guidelines for the secondary prevention population.

The variables which independently predicted outcome, with relevant “weighting factors” included in the final validated **REACT** score include age, sex, postcode (as a marker of socioeconomic status), whether or not the patient’s initial presentation was with stable disease (e.g. angina) or an acute event (e.g. myocardial infarction of stroke), smoking status, diabetes mellitus, dementia, liver disease, hypertension, eGFR and very high levels of non-HDL cholesterol.

The REACT score has now been successfully validated using the data contained within the SAIL database, where the model is highly predictive of a person’s five-year risk of having a recurrent atherosclerotic cardiovascular event when compared to the observed risk for the person.

We have also incorporated an adjustment factor that calculated the expected absolute reduction in LDL cholesterol with addition of PCSK9 therapy (-60%) from which we can calculate the expected relative reduction in major ASCVD events and all-cause mortality (-21% and -10% per 1mmol/L reduction) and thus derive the expected absolute reduction in risk of ASCVD events and mortality.

Outputs from the model suggest that (at least in the Welsh population) the criteria for addition of PCSK9 therapy would be most appropriately be based on estimated absolute levels and expected reduction in risk of ASCVD events and mortality with treatment, rather than LDL-C thresholds of 4mmol/L for general ASCVD secondary prevention and 3.5mmol/L secondary prevention in ASCVD with recurrent events +/- familial hypercholesterolaemia.

2.2.7.1 Case studies using the new risk calculator

Two case studies have been provided showing examples of using the new REACT risk calculator.

2.2.7.1.1 Case 1

A 60-year-old male, ex-smoker free from other risk factors presenting with stable angina who lives in central Swansea with an LDL-cholesterol of 4.2mmol/L and no other MRFs on maximally tolerated statin therapy.

Figure 18. Predicted-observed risk decile plot, for model calibration for all patients included and according to entry point.

2.2.7 Development of a risk calculator based the Phase 1 findings

A second important part of phase 1 was to take the learnings from analysis of ASCVD outcomes and use this information to develop a new risk-prediction model for major adverse cardiac events in patients with established disease.

Clinicians worldwide are very familiar with the use of risk estimation models for identifying those at risk in the primary prevention setting – i.e. individuals, without clinical ACSVD but at increased risk of developing the condition over the next 10 years, for whom prescription of drug therapy would be considered clinically beneficial to reduce their risk of ASCVD.

This patient would be eligible for PCSK9 antibody therapy according to NICE guidance. The REACT calculator estimates that his absolute 5 year risk of ASCVD would be 14% and that his 5 year risk would be reduced to 7% by addition of evolocumab.

This equates to an absolute 5 year risk reduction of 7%.

2.2.7.1.2 Case 2

A 60 year old male ex-smoker with diabetes mellitus, hypertension and an eGFR of 35 presenting with a myocardial infarction with an LDL-C of 3.2 on maximally tolerated statin therapy who lives in central Swansea.

This patient would not be eligible for PCSK9 antibody therapy according to NICE guidelines.

Figure 19. Diagrams of REACT risk calculator output for the two case studies.

The REACT calculator estimates his absolute 5 year risk of an ASCVD event would be 36% and that his 5 year risk would be reduced to 21% by addition of Evolocumab.

This risk reduction equates to an absolute 5 year risk reduction of 15%, which is more than twice the absolute risk reduction expected from the addition of evolocumab in case 1 in whom this treatment is endorsed by NICE guidance, with associated greater cost-effectiveness of therapy.

Whilst the model still requires external validation in an external population wide patient dataset, the model is already indicating several interesting trends. Our data make a strong argument to consider a more accurate clinical risk estimation-based approach for escalation of secondary prevention therapy in clinical practice.

2.3 Phase 1 Conclusions

2.3.1 Increasing burden and reduction in risk factor management

A key goal of phase 1 is to better understand the current situation with regards to ASCVD including prevalence and incidence of disease as well as understanding how well the condition is being managed in Wales.

The proportion of the population with diagnosed ASCVD in Wales has increased by about 0.5 % from 2010 to 2022 (from 8.9% to 9.4%), indicating a significant increase in the burden of ASCVD. This represents approximately 30,000 additional people requiring care provision within NHS Wales.

In addition, the prevalence of DM has also increased over this same period (from 2010 to 2022) by around 1.7%.

In parallel with the increasing disease burden, there appears to be a substantial and growing gap in the delivery of effective treatment/management of risk factors of people living with and at increased risk of ASCVD, particularly with regard to lipid management in the ASCVD and DM populations.

Whilst the use of high-intensity statin therapy has increased in the ASCVD population (from 9.4% to 25.2%) over the period 2010 to 2022. The use of non-high-intensity statin therapy significantly reduced from 59.6% to 38.2%

over the same period, with the percentage of people with ASCVD receiving no treatment for lowering their lipid levels rising to 31% (an increase of 6% since 2010). Prescribing of LLT, including HI-statin therapy, documentation of LDL-C and achievement of target LDL-C levels was low, especially in PAD patients.

In addition, there is documented evidence fewer than half of the ASCVD patients are achieving target a target LDL-C level of <1.8 mmol/L, even when their lipid levels are checked!

This trend is further illustrated for patients with DM, where over the same period prescription of statins (and other lipid lowering therapy) for people living with DM fell by 5.7%, with only around 50% of the DM population achieving the ESC target LDL-C of <1.8 mmol/L. Although target achievement in "tested patients" increased over time, the proportion of patients undergoing lipid testing declined. More rigorous lipid management requires prioritisation, especially for PAD and stroke patients. Increasing incidence and prevalence of DM, together with decreasing quality of risk factor management will lead to worse health outcomes in the population if not addressed more effectively.

The impact of poor management is clearly illustrated by our findings that the majority of patients who suffered a fatal or non-fatal MI or Stroke as their first presentation of ASCVD (2010-23) had suboptimal testing treatment and control of their lipids and or blood pressure in the year before the index event, even if they had a clinical documentation of one or more major ASCVD risk factors (hypertension, CKD, Diabetes Mellitus [DM]) in their record prior to presentation.

Use of a secondary prevention risk calculator will permit more accurate assessment of a patient's risk aiding clinical decision makers and healthcare providers/payers to provide more effective high value care to our patients with ASCVD.

3 Phase 2: Implementation and evaluation of novel high risk CVD management clinics

3.1 Phase 2 overview

3.1.1 Evaluation of pilot high-risk CVD Risk management clinics: Undertake an evaluation of effectiveness, acceptability and value of specialist pharmacist-led optimisation of lipids and BP in high-risk patients

Phase 2 focuses on the design, implementation and evaluation of pharmacist led, MDT supported ASCVD risk management clinics. These clinics aimed to optimise risk factor management (blood pressure and/or lipids) in patients with or at high-risk of ASCVD. The clinics were implemented across two regional health boards (Swansea Bay and Hywel Dda University Health Boards) in rural and urban Wales. The evaluation considers the efficacy, feasibility, barriers, economics and acceptability to patients and healthcare professionals.

The goals included:

- Provide a holistic approach to health and care needs
- *Optimise therapeutic management* of patients (lipid and Blood pressure levels)
- *Transform the ways of working* for our clinicians and healthcare professionals, by providing a new method of delivering care
- Develop a *Value Based Healthcare* approach to inform the requirements of the service.
- Support the independence and wellbeing of our population, by offering education around *healthy living*.

As part of the collaboration between all parties a list of milestones was developed (see table 4).

Table 3. Milestones for phase 2 of the project.

Project phase	Milestones
Phase 2:	Agree evidence based Cardiovascular Risk Protocol (to include lipid modification as key risk factor, alongside overall CV risk) (Sep'22). Protocol will be in line with current national/international guidelines e.g. ESC and aligned to current drug licenses and guidance e.g. NICE/AWMSG
	A Clinical evaluation using 3 different models (supported by JCRF) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual Practice • Community Hub • Secondary Care
	Evaluation will determine most effective model for both patients and service and will assess <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. deployment of allied health professionals to support implementation utilising the agreed CV Risk protocol. AHPs will have prescribing authorisation in line with agreed protocol 2. Patient survey – qualitative research 3. Deployment of digital support to HCPs/Patients e.g. Patients Know Best. This will support communication across service and patients, education to patients and capture of PROMs/PREMs
	Patients reviewed at 1st clinics (Oct'22) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aim to assess 40-50 patients in each setting • Assess 6-8 patients per clinic (dependant on clinical experience) • Follow up and review
	Health Economic Impact report published

Figure 20. Map showing the geographical location of the two health boards involved in phase 2 of the programme.

3.1.2 Phase 2 Service Design

To improve the clinical outcomes for CVD patients, National guidelines (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) and the European Society of Cardiology (ESC)) recommend a focus upon the detection and management of the high-risk conditions: **blood pressure & cholesterol**. In response to these recommendations phase two involves the creation of several specialised pharmacist led high risk CVD management clinics, that involve high intensity monitoring and management of patients' blood pressure & lipid levels through specialised therapeutic management and general lifestyle guidance.

As part of the design of the project two (of the seven) health boards in Wales are involved in Phase 2 (Hywel Dda UHB & Swansea Bay UHB), covering the whole southwest region of Wales (see Figure 20).

3.1.2.1 Hywel Dda UHB

Hywel Dda University Health Board (H DUHB) provides healthcare services to approximately 385,600 people across Carmarthenshire, Ceredigion, and Pembrokeshire. There are four district general hospitals: Glangwili General Hospital with around 403 beds, Bronglais General Hospital with 155 beds, Prince Philip Hospital hold approximately 218 beds, and Wityhush General Hospital 213 beds. H DUHB employs

approximately 9,500 staff members and offers a comprehensive range of primary, community, mental health, and secondary care services. There are 48 GP practices across its region. These practices are grouped into clusters to promote integrated care and resource sharing. The health board also manages several practices directly, where independent GP services have transitioned to health board management.

3.1.2.2 Swansea Bay UHB

Swansea Bay University Health Board (SBUHB) serves approximately 390,000 people across Swansea and Neath Port Talbot. It operates three main hospital sites:

Morrison Hospital providing approximately 750 including both a major trauma centre and the regional Cardiology and Cardiothoracic centres; Singleton Hospital with around 550 beds; and Neath Port Talbot Hospital with approximately 200 beds. In total, the health board oversees around 1,500 hospital beds and employs over 14,000 staff. SBUHB maintains strong academic links with Swansea University, supporting clinical training and research initiatives.

There are 45 GP practices within its area. These practices are organised into clusters that facilitate collaboration among GPs, dentists, community pharmacies, and other healthcare providers to deliver integrated care.

3.1.3 A Bespoke ASCVD Prevention Service

This second phase of the collaboration seeks to assess patients with or at high-risk of ASCVD and evaluate the feasibility, efficacy and understand the barriers to delivery of ASCVD risk factor management. Three different clinic settings were set up to ascertain which type of clinic is most effective, these included:

- A Primary Care Hub
- Individual GP surgeries
- A Secondary Care Hub

Both health boards would aim to recruit around 75 patients each which would be used to base an evaluation of the different service models in practice (See Figure 20).

3.1.3.1 Why were the three different clinic settings chosen?

Three different clinic settings were chosen to understand feasibility, barriers, efficacy and patient preferences in different settings. A secondary

care hub model was implemented within urban Swansea, for a more rural community such as in Hywel Dda UHB a community hub model was chosen where several GP practice or a GP cluster can feed into one central location. In addition to these two models a third model that involves the prevention clinics being delivered in individual practices will also be carried out. We chose to use GP practices from both Swansea Bay and Hywel Dda regions will be used to explore this third model (figure 21).

3.1.3.2 Hywel Dda University Health Board Clinics

We aimed to recruit 25 patients to clinics delivered in two GP practices (one in Carmarthenshire and one in Pembrokeshire), and 50 patients to a primary care hub in Ceredigion.

3.1.3.3 Swansea Bay University Health Board Clinics

We aimed to recruit 25 patients to a GP practice within Swansea Bay UHB and a further 50 patients to the secondary care hub.

3.1.4 Aims of the CVD prevention service in Phase 2

There are several key aims associated with the service delivered by the CVD prevention clinic models in phase 2, these include:

- Review feasibility of delivery of care in different venues, utilising expert clinical pharmacists.
- Identify High CVD risk patients (Secondary and Primary Prevention) with suboptimal Lipid/BP control.
- Review risk factor management
- Optimise treatment of uncontrolled lipids and BP (according to NICE guidance and ESC/EAS treatment targets)
- Provide support and guidance on 'healthy living'.
- Identify any other relevant patient concerns that could be "signposted" to other clinical service areas as appropriate

3.1.5 Regulatory Considerations for the Service

In November 2022, the proposed *innovation in practice assessing a new pathway for optimising medical management of CVD*, was reviewed by the Joint Study Review Committee (JSRC) at Swansea Bay University Health Board. The Committee conducted an independent assessment of the project, evaluating its scientific merit and its classification as an innovation in practice rather than formal research.

Following this review, the JSRC confirmed that the initiative met the criteria for a service evaluation and was appropriately designated as a non-research, innovation in practice project.

3.1.6 Service Staff

The service was delivered by a multidisciplinary specialist team comprising prescribing pharmacists with expertise in cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk management and prevention, supported by research nurses, and overseen through clinical governance provided by two consultant cardiologists.

3.1.7 Recruitment into the service

Participating general practices were invited to identify patients either diagnosed with or at high risk of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD), who exhibited uncontrolled lipid profiles, specifically elevated LDL-C or non-HDL-C levels, based on predefined eligibility criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

- A history of established vascular disease (CAD, stroke, PAD)
- Without vascular disease but considered to be at high risk (E.g. Diabetes mellitus etc) with a QRISK score >10%

With

- LDL>2.6 and non-HDL >3.4, and/or
- Systolic BP >160mmHg and <180mmHg

Exclusion Criteria

- Heart Failure
- CKD stage > 4
- Other severe clinical comorbidities
- Patients with complex social or care needs
- Unable to attend clinics

The GP practices sent invites to patients they had identified as meeting the inclusion criteria through the process outlined above. Following confirmation that the patient would like to take part a member of the clinic team contacted them patient and discuss the procedures in more detail. All clinics were staffed with an experienced research nurse and a senior pharmacist with experience in CVD medication prescribing. Patients attending the various clinics followed the pathway as depicted in Figure 21.

Figure 21. Diagram showing the different clinic venues and how they are divided between the 2 Health boards taking part.

3.1.8 Phase 2 Patient Pathway Design

A single care pathway was designed with follow up for up to 52 weeks (figure 22). The patient were managed by the clinic staff at each of the sites. Extra visits and recalls were arranged when required depending upon how the patient needed to be managed.

3.1.8.1 Patient Assessment(s)

As part of the service, each patient underwent blood testing to assess their lipid profile, glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c), and renal function (urea and electrolytes). In addition, comprehensive data were collected, including past medical and medication history, demographic information, patient-reported experience measures (PREMs), patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs), and blood pressure readings (see Table 4).

3.1.8.1.1 Baseline Visit 1a

Visit 1a was undertaken by the nurse and included screening for suitability, Patients had the procedures fully explained and any questions answered before giving consent to this management plan. At this appointment, venous bloods and point of care (POC) Lipid profile, and HbA1c and U+E's were performed.

3.1.8.1.2 Baseline visit 1b.

At Visit 1b, patients were reviewed by a specialist pharmacist who assessed blood pressure readings, recent lipid profiles, and other relevant clinical parameters. A structured medication review was conducted in alignment with NICE guidelines (Appendix 2). Prescriptions were issued using FP10 forms and dispensed through the patients' designated community pharmacies.

In addition to clinical evaluation, patients were asked to provide contextual information regarding their living arrangements, understanding of their medical condition, typical levels of physical activity during an average week, and current employment status. Standardised questionnaires used to capture these data are included in Appendices 3, 4, and 5, respectively.

3.1.8.1.3 Subsequent visits (visits 2-4)

All patients were requested a to attend visit 2, within 4 to 8 weeks of the baseline visit, to review clinical status and response to prescription changes at visit 1b. Following Visit 2, patients requiring

further treatment optimisation were invited for further review depending on risk factor control and their responses to changes in treatment. Where patients' risk factor control is deemed to have been optimised no further review in the clinical centre was required until the final visit. However, patients were given contact details and be encouraged to contact the clinic nurse to report any new (clinical) concerns. The clinic nurse also contacted patients every 6 weeks to confirm all is well.

Table 4. A table showing the different assessments carried out at each visit along the patient pathway.

Activity	Baseline		Visit 2	Visit 3-4	Final Visit 5
	Visit 1a	Visit 1b			
Consent	*				
Medical history	*				
Current Medication	*		*	*	*
Blood Pressure	*	*	*	*	*
Pulse	*		*	*	*
Height	*				
Weight	*		*	*	*
BMI	*		*	*	*
QRISK-3 score (for patients without clinical CVD)		*			*
Blood Lipid screen (Lab) Lipid screen POC (clinic) HbA1c/U&Es	*		*	*	*
PROMS/ EQ 5D	*				*
Patient/Carer experience survey					*
Selected patient/ staff interview (s)					*

3.1.8.1.4 Final Visit (12 months)

At the final visit all patients had their blood pressure and lipids evaluated and were then discharged to their GP. Following this final visit, patients were discharged back to their local GP for ongoing CVD management. Results from the final visit and further recommendations were sent to their GPs.

3.1.8.2 Tasks and interventions in the clinics.

In addition to optimisation of lipid and blood pressure control, patients were provided with fitness and diet advice. Patients with a high BMI (>30) are also recommended the DASH Diet (<https://www.heartuk.org.uk/dietary-patterns/dash>) and provided materials to help guide them. The dash diet is aimed at promoting a healthy balanced diet to reduce weight and utilises food known to have blood pressure lowering potential. Healthy living and smoking cessation advice and signposting

is also provided to all patients where required.

3.2 Phase 2 Service and Evaluation Outline

A key part of phase 2 is to evaluate the effectiveness and affordability of the Pilot CVD prevention clinics outlined above. The evaluation reviewed the feasibility of delivery of care in different settings with a focus on both the value and the achievement of prudent health care principles [14] which include:

1. Achieving health and well-being with the public, patients and professionals as equal partners through co-production.
2. Care for those with the greatest health need first, making the most effective use of all skills and resources.

3. Do only what is needed, no more, no less; and do no harm.
4. Reduce inappropriate variation using evidence-based practices consistently and transparently.

3.2.1 Aims of the evaluation

The aim of this real-world evaluation was to understand benefits to patients, staff, and the health board for the new service for managing high risk CVD patients. This focused on:

1. Assessing the implementation of the different CVD risk prevention clinics including barriers and enablers of success.
2. Evaluating the impact on health of a CVD risk factors
3. Assessing the acceptability of the different clinic models for patients and practitioners.
4. Asses the VBHC case of the different clinic models (i.e. what are the outcomes in view of the costs associated with each model);
5. A Health Economic Impact Assessment (“HEIA”) to evaluate and ensure the model has the potential to be sustained across NHS Wales and rolled out across other geographies
6. Understanding the value prospect of a validated point of care (POC) measurement for Blood Lipids (Total Cholesterol, HDL-cholesterol [“good” Cholesterol], LDL and Non-HDL Cholesterol [“bad” Cholesterol] and triglyceride levels) compared to standard laboratory test results.

3.2.2 Value Plan for the evaluation of the Service

The plan for assessing the value of this new service will focus on several key aspects. These key aspects will include:

- Impact on Health
 - o Effectiveness of the services in risk factor management
 - o Explore the difference between the varied service environments
 - o Staff and Patient Experience
- Cost-Effectiveness and economic Analysis
- Barriers to implementation
- Limitations, Conclusions, & Value Assessment
- Recommendations

3.2.2.1 Impact on Health

To asses the impact on health of the CVD prevention clinic several sets of data were collected these included:

Patient recruitment, retention and demographics: the recruitment process, retention of people in the clinics and patient demographics across the 3 clinic settings.

Effectiveness of the services: analysis of the patient outcome data and PROMs/ PREMs to assess the effectiveness of the service in managing CVD patients.

Difference in the Service Models: Explore the key differences observed in the patient data for the different health boards and models of delivery for the services.

Staff and Patient Experience: Stakeholder interviews with patients and staff were conducted across both HBs. Tol explore patients experiences and expectations of the service as well and enablers and barriers of using/providing the service.

3.2.2.2 Cost-Effectiveness and Economic Analysis

a cost-effectiveness analysis was carried out to determine the economic cost and value. It compared current service costs and extrapolate the cost/benefit of the new service, against measures such as reduction in hospital visits and benefit of well controlled lipid and BP. A Health Economic Impact Assessment (“HEIA”) to evaluate and ensure the model has the potential to be sustained across NHS Wales and rolled out across other geographies.

3.2.2.3 Barriers to Implementation

An essential component of the value analysis involves examining the barriers and enablers associated with the implementation of the service. To investigate these factors, qualitative data were collected through interviews with key stakeholders involved in the service delivery, alongside documentation of events throughout the project’s progression. This evaluative process led to the identification of key recommendations to inform the future rollout and implementation of the service across other areas within the Health Board and potentially in other regions of Wales.

3.2.2.4 Limitations, Conclusions & Recommendations

The study concluded with the identification of several limitations, which inform directions for future research. The evaluation and value assessment of the new service will employ a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative data from interviews and surveys with staff and patients, alongside quantitative analysis of evolving patterns of service demand. This comprehensive methodology aims to assess the cost-effectiveness of the service and ultimately determine its broader applicability and value for wider implementation across the health system.

3.2.3 Data Collection and Data Sources

For this evaluation a mixed methods approach will be undertaken:

3.2.3.1 Quantitative Approach

As the study is an evaluation of the service, there is no control group to compare the patient groups with. In addition to understand the value provided by the new service, patient outcomes were recorded to compare with the overall costs of providing the service. Patients outcomes included:

- Recruitment and retention data
- Changes in lipid profile throughout involvement in the study.
 - o Including point of care lipid measurements
- Changes in blood pressure throughout involvement in the study.
- Changes to medication and other clinical variables
- PROMS and PREMs
 - o Including staff and patient perspectives on using an electronic patient record.

3.2.3.2 Qualitative Approach

The qualitative data collection focused on both the patients and staff experiences and expectations of the service for the Staff and Patient Experience section in the Impact on health.

3.2.3.2.1 Patients

A key part of the Value-Based approach is to determine the benefits and disadvantages of the new service. With a focus placed upon the value of the service, including if the patient has seen benefits and disadvantages to the service. Patients were asked to complete a patient experience questionnaire at the end of the study to determine their overall experience with the new service, and where improvements could be made.

3.2.3.2.2 Direct Care Staff

Staff directly involved were interviewed, to determine how they have perceived the service, and the benefits and disadvantages they have experienced in providing the service. Staff were also asked to discuss the barriers and facilitators of the service, which will help to determine how future iterations of the service can be improved. Interviews will be analysed using a thematic approach.

4 Phase 2 : Clinical Pathway Service Evaluation

4.1 Impact on Health

4.1.1 Patient recruitment

Patient Recruitment began in Swansea in May 2023 and was completed at the beginning of March 2024. Recruitment in HDUHB was delayed initially due to the issues surrounding IG and began at the end of Sept 2023 finishing in early March 2024.

Both sites have now completed the full recruitment of their patients into the service (157 in total: 50 in Secondary Care; 50 in the Primary Care Hub; 57 in their GP practices).

SBUHB had a slower but steadier rise in recruitment which was primarily due to the challenges with GP practice engagement. Due to governance arrangements around IG, SBUHB had to rely on the GP practices to carry out the searches and send out the letters. HDDUHB experienced a significant delay in being able to start recruitment in both the community Hub and GP practices due to delays in obtaining IG permissions, resulting in an additional 4-month delay. Despite this the teams in HDDUHB were able to recruit more rapidly once this was resolved, as the service delivery teams were responsible for the patient searches and letters.

Figure 23. Graph of total recruitment into the service(s) over time at both health boards.

4.1.1.1 Swansea Bay Recruitment Summary

Initial searches carried out in the GP practices in SBUHB identified over 600 potentially eligible patients with ASCVD or at high ASCVD risk who had evidence of uncontrolled lipids and or BP

according to latest results entered in the system. The primary care teams sent out the referral letters themselves to the identified patients, who were required by agreed IG to contact the CVD prevention clinic team themselves if they wanted to take part.

The response rate to the initial invitation letters was approximately 25%. However, upon further assessment by the CVD prevention team at Swansea Bay University Health Board, 71% of respondents were excluded, primarily due to acceptable blood pressure and lipid levels identified during the screening visit. This necessitated a secondary screening process within the CVD prevention clinics, requiring substantial time and resources. While this step excluded a significant proportion of participants from the care pathway, it also served as a valuable mechanism for confirming effective contemporary risk factor control among these individuals.

Due to information governance (IG) agreements, responsibility for patient searches and participant identification could not be delegated to the CVD prevention clinic team. Consequently, these tasks remained with individual general practices, where competing workload pressures led to delays in both the completion of searches and the communication of results. This had a substantial impact on the project's recruitment timeline. Recruitment ultimately spanned approximately 10 months, from 29 May 2023 to 3 March 2024, significantly exceeding the original estimate of 3 to 5 months. It is anticipated that a unified search and recruitment process would have enabled adherence to the initial timeline.

One notable positive outcome of the CVD prevention programme was its role in raising awareness of the scale of cardiovascular risk within the local population and catalysing action beyond the scope of the formal prevention clinics. Initially, several general practices within the Swansea Bay University Health Board (SBUHB) area were identified as primary recruitment sites for the programme. However, prior to the commencement of the formal evaluation, and following their agreement to participate, practices within two clusters independently initiated reviews of their own 'at-risk' CVD patient populations. These internal audits led to proactive optimisation of blood pressure and lipid-lowering therapies. As a result of these interventions, a substantial number of patients no longer met the eligibility criteria for inclusion in the prevention service. This unintended but beneficial outcome highlights the programme's wider influence in prompting earlier clinical engagement and improving risk factor control at the primary care level.

4.1.1.2 Hywel Dda Recruitment Summary.

Following consultation with primary care leads at Hywel Dda University Health Board (HDDUHB), it was agreed that the CVD prevention team would assume full responsibility for patient screening, identification, and invitation processes. This decision aimed to minimise the burden on already stretched primary care services. Information governance (IG) approval for this approach was subsequently granted by HDDUHB, although this was delayed due to protracted communication and approval processes involving Digital Health and Care Wales (DHCW), the data controller for the majority of general practices and clusters in Wales (excluding managed practices). As a result, recruitment within HDDUHB was delayed by approximately five months.

Once initiated, patient searches conducted across participating general practices identified over 700 individuals potentially eligible for the CVD prevention clinic. Response rates from practices in Pembrokeshire and Carmarthenshire were consistent with those observed in Swansea Bay University Health Board (SBUHB), at approximately 25%. However, recruitment to the community hub clinic demonstrated a higher response rate of approximately 40%. Notably, the proportion of patients excluded during the screening process was significantly lower in HDDUHB compared to SBUHB (31% vs. 70%, respectively).

Despite a three-week pause over the 2023 Christmas period, recruitment in HDDUHB was completed within five months, with the first patient enrolled on 2 October 2023 and the final patient on 28 February 2024. The most likely explanation for the difference in recruitment rate between the two UHBs is that the searches and initial invitations were conducted primarily by the clinic delivery team with input from the practice staff as necessary in HDUHB, rather than relying on the primary care staff alone in SBUHB, with their many competing commitments.

The integrated approach to searches permitted by HDDUHB seemed to be more effective in identifying patients best suited for this new service, despite the significant delays due to governance issues.

4.1.2 Patient Demographics

The patient demographic information was collected from patient notes and the patient general lifestyle questionnaire (Appendix 4). When comparing the results from the GP clinic in SBUHB and HDUHB the only significant difference observed was the percentage of people with diabetes, which was significantly ($p=0.002$) higher in the HDUHB GP clinics. Whilst the SBUHB did show higher percentages of people with hypertension ($p=0.09$) and hyperlipidaemia ($p=0.2$) these differences were not significant. we observed significantly ($p<0.05$) raised BMI values (see table 5) across both sexes compared to the national average. A breakdown of the different clinics can be seen below:

4.1.2.1 Secondary Care Hub Demographics

Females 57%, Males, 43%. Mean Age 65.9y Hypertension 73.6%, Diabetes 63.7%, Dyslipidaemia 39.6%, BMI 32.2+/-8.3kg/

m2 (36% overweight, 56% Obese) Current smokers 24%, Ex Smokers 40%.

4.1.2.2 Community Hub Patient Demographics

Females 55% Males 45%. Mean Age 70.3y Hypertension 60%, Diabetes 84%, Dyslipidaemia 57% BMI 29.4+/-5.9kg/m2 (36% overweight, 38% Obese) Current smokers 15%, Ex Smokers 48%

4.1.2.3 GP Practices Demographics

Females 51% Males 49%. Mean Age 64.4y Hypertension 70%, Diabetes 69%, Dyslipidaemia 67% BMI 29.4+/-5.9kg/m2 (32% overweight, 58% Obese) Current smokers 25%, Ex Smokers 40%.

4.1.2.4 Other Comorbidities

Patients across all three clinics settings presented with a range of comorbidities. Only a small proportion had a history of serious comorbidities such as Cancer or clinically significant liver disease or CKD.

Table 5. Primary and secondary prevention patients per site.

Site	Overall patient numbers	Primary prevention number	Primary prevention number
Total	157	106	51
Hywel Dda Primary care hub	50	45	5
Hywel General Practice	27	20	7
Swansea Bay Secondary care hub	50	22	28
Swansea Bay General Practice	30	19	11

Table 6. Mean QRISK score for primary prevention patients per site.

Site	Primary prevention Patient numbers	QRISK score, Mean (SD)
Total	106	22(11.2)
Hywel Dda Primary care hub	45	20.1 (9.4)
Hywel General Practice	20	20.5 (12.5)
Swansea Bay Secondary care hub	22	31.8 (18.5)
Swansea Bay General Practice	19	17.2 (10.7)

Figure 24. QRISK distribution across all primary prevention patients (n=106).

4.1.3 Impact on Lipids and Blood Pressure

A total of 157 patients were recruited into the evaluation, including 106 primary prevention patients (table 5) with a mean QRISK 10-year CVD risk score of 22% (SD=11.2) (table 6 and figure 24).

Of this group 31 patient had a documented non-HDL-C at both visit 1 (mean non-HDL-C =4.1mmol/L (SD=1.0) and at visit 5 (mean non-HDL-C=3.1mmol/L (SD=1.2) with a mean reduction of 0.89mmol/L (figure 25).

4.1.3.1 Lipid Management

4.1.3.1.1 Secondary prevention patients

A total of 51 secondary prevention patients had non-HDL-C documented at visit 1 with a mean non-HDL-C of 4.0 mmol/L.

A total of 48 patients had documented LDL-C at visit 1 (mean LDL-C=3.1mmol/L (SD=0.94). Of these 29 patients had both first visit LDL-C documented (mean 3.2mmol/L (SD=0.97) and final visit LDL-C (mean = 2.4mmol/L (SD=0.92)) and a mean reduction of 0.89mmol/L (figure 26).

Figure 25. Reduction in non-HDL-C in secondary prevention patients (N=31).

Figure 26. Reduction in LDL-C in secondary prevention patients (N=29).

Figure 27. Reduction in non-HDL-C in primary prevention patients (N=71).

Figure 28. Reduction in LDL-C in primary prevention patients (N=67).

Figure 29. Reduction in systolic blood pressure in secondary prevention patients (N=34).

Figure 30. Reduction in systolic blood pressure in secondary prevention patients with uncontrolled BP at first visit (N=16).

Of the 29 secondary prevention patients who had lipids recorded at the final visit, only 11 (38%) achieved an LDL-C $\leq 1.8\text{mmol/L}$. No patients had an LDL-C >math>\geq 4.0\text{mmol/L}</math> (the NICE threshold for PCSK9-Mab for secondary prevention).

4.1.3.1.2 Primary prevention lipid analysis

Altogether 105 primary prevention patients had a mean starting non-HDL cholesterol of 4.1mmol/L (SD=0.79). Of this group 71 patients also had a recorded Non-HDL-C at their first visit (mean Non-HDL-C =4.1mmol/L (SD=0.8) and at their final visit (mean non-HDL-C=2.9mmol/L (SD=0.9) with an overall reduction of 1.18mmol/L (figure 27).

A total of 98 patients had a documented LDL-C at the first visit with a mean of 3.1mmol/L (SD=0.76). Of this group, 67 also had a documented LDL-C at their first visit (mean LDL-C=3.1mmol/L (SD=0.8) and at their final visit (mean LDL-C=2.2mmol/L (SD=0.8) and overall achieved a mean reduction of 0.9mmol/L (figure 28).

4.1.3.2 Blood Pressure

4.1.3.2.1 Blood Pressure Control in Secondary prevention

In total, 51 secondary prevention patients had blood pressure documented at visit 1, with an overall mean systolic BP of 142mmHg.

Of this group 34 had a documented blood pressure at both visit 1 (mean systolic BP =142mmHg SD=8) and at visit 5 (mean systolic BP =132.2mmHg (SD=13) with a mean reduction of systolic BP of 9.1mmHg (figure 29).

A total of 16 patients had a systolic BP >140mmHg at the first clinic and had documented BP at the final visit. Overall, this group achieved a mean reduction of 16.1mmHg in systolic BP (figure 30).

4.1.3.2.2 Primary prevention blood pressure analysis

Of the 106 primary prevention patients recruited, 105 patients had blood pressure recorded at visit 1 (one patient declined). The mean systolic blood pressure at this visit was 147.3mmHg (SD=18.4).

Of these patients, 81 also had a blood pressure recorded at visit 1 (mean systolic = 147.7mmHg (SD=18.5) and at visit 5 (mean systolic =131.7mmHg (SD=14.5) with an overall average reduction in systolic BP of 16.3mmHg (figure 31).

4.1.3.2.3 Blood pressure reduction in primary prevention patients with uncontrolled blood pressure

A total of 38 primary prevention patients had a recorded systolic blood pressure >=150mmHg at visit one and also attended the final clinic. Overall, this group achieved a mean reduction of 30.7mmHg across the study period (figure 32).

Figure 31. Mean systolic blood pressure in primary prevention patients at first and final clinic visit (N=81).

Figure 32. Reduction in systolic blood pressure in primary prevention patients an initial systolic BP >=150mmHg (N=38).

Fifty-two patients had an initial systolic BP ≥ 140 mmHg recorded at visit 1 and attended the final visit. Overall, this group achieved a mean reduction of 26mmHg in systolic BP across the study period. (figure 33).

Figure 33. Reduction in systolic blood pressure in primary prevention patients an initial systolic BP ≥ 140 mmHg (N=52).

4.1.4 Service activities

Key activities and outcomes in delivering the service included:

4.1.4.1 Patient Retention and Clinic Attendance

A key indicator of success for a cardiovascular disease (CVD) prevention clinic is its capacity to retain patients throughout the duration of the intervention. The current model is structured around a 12-month follow-up period, during which patients' blood pressure and lipid levels are monitored and managed through lifestyle modification and pharmacological optimisation. The effectiveness of this model is contingent upon sustained patient engagement and consistent attendance at scheduled review appointments.

The clinic pathway comprises six face-to-face visits (designated as Visits 1A, 1B, 2, 3, 4, and 5) and five interim telephone consultations. Attendance at Visits 1A, 1B, 2, and 5 was mandatory for all participants, while Visits 3 and 4 were utilised at the discretion of the clinical team, particularly in cases where patients exhibited

suboptimal control of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) or blood pressure. Additional in-person reviews could also be arranged by the CVD prevention team in response to clinical concerns or persistent difficulty in achieving target lipid and blood pressure levels. A higher frequency of visits was generally indicative of more complex cases requiring intensified management.

4.1.4.1.1 Secondary Care Hub Retention and attendance

Over the period of the evaluation a total of 14 patients (of the 50) (28%) did not complete the full 52-week review in the secondary care hub. Of these 14 patients, 8 were referred to other secondary care clinics. 2 patients withdrew to family or stress related conditions (unrelated to the service), 1 person died, and 3 others were lost to follow up and stopped attending clinics.

In total there were 231 clinic visits carried out at the Secondary Care Hub. Attendance at the Secondary Care Hub clinic was excellent over the first 3 mandatory visits (Visit 1A, 1B and 2) at 92% retention (see figure 23). Interestingly visit 3 and 4 were only needed for 30 and 19 of the patients respectively, and no unscheduled visits were required, showing that approximately 17% and 47% of patients were well controlled by week 24 and week 36 respectively. Of the 36 patients who completed the full 52 weeks at the secondary care hub clinic each patient attended an average of 5.3 ± 0.6 visits.

4.1.4.1.2 Community Hub Retention and attendance

Over the period of the evaluation a total of 19 patients (of the 50) (38%) did not complete the full 52-week review. Including: two patients either declined, did not attend clinics or did not respond to telephone calls, one patient was referred to secondary care clinic (cardiology) and a further three were withdrawn due to other medical complexities and referred to alternative services. One patient declined the clinic as they reported they were too busy and travelling to the Hub was difficult.

In total there were 257 clinic visits carried out at the Community Hub. Attendance at the Community Hub clinic was excellent over the first 3 mandatory visits (Visit 1A, 1B and 2)

at 94% retention (see figure 23). Interestingly visit 3 and 4 were needed for 36 and 18 of the patients respectively, showing that approximately 16% and 58% of patients were well controlled by week 24 and week 36 respectively.

In addition, 5 of the patients required an additional unscheduled visit and 2 patients required 4 additional unscheduled Visits. Of the 43 patients who completed the full 52 weeks at the Community hub clinic each patient attended an average of 5.6 ± 1.7 visits.

4.1.4.1.3 GP Clinics Retention and Attendance

At the Swansea Bay GP practice 6 of the 25 (24%) patients recruited did not complete the 52-week clinic, including 1 patient referred to the Lipid Clinic, 1 moved out of

the area, and 4 were lost to follow up.

At the two GP practices in Hywel Dda a total of 7 of the 25 (28%) patients recruited did not complete the full 52-week clinic. The reasons provided for these 7 patients were that they either declined to attend/did not attend clinics or did not respond to telephone calls.

In total there were 260 clinic visits (121 at the SBUHB GP clinics and 139 at the HDUHB GP clinics) carried out at the GP clinics. Attendance at the GP clinic at SBUHB and HDUHB was comparable over the first 3 mandatory visits (Visit 1A, 1B and 2) when compared to the Secondary Care and Community Hubs, at 88% and 92% retention (see figure 34).

Figure 34. Figure showing the attendance at each of the clinic visits for all the different clinic settings.

4.1.5 Changes in Medication

A central objective of the CVD prevention clinic was the optimisation of pharmacological therapy, particularly lipid-lowering and antihypertensive medications. On average, patients enrolled in the clinic underwent 2.1 ± 0.7 medication adjustments over the course of the programme. At Visit 1b, the initial consultation with the specialist pharmacist, 70% of patients had at least one medication change.

This proportion varied by clinic setting: 88% in the secondary care hub, 52% in the community hub, 75% in the Swansea Bay University Health Board

(SBUHB) GP clinics, and 79% in the Hywel Dda University Health Board (HDDUHB) GP clinics.

By the conclusion of the 12-month intervention, all patients who completed the programme had experienced some form of medication modification. Among these individuals, 38% (n = 36) were prescribed high-intensity statins, 59% (n = 55) were on moderate-intensity statins, and 6% (n = 6) were maintained on low-intensity statins. Additionally, 3% (n = 3) were prescribed bempedoic acid, and 3% (n = 3) received evolocumab. A detailed breakdown of lipid-lowering medication changes by clinic site is presented in the next pages.

In the secondary care hub it was found that 36 people who finished the full clinic service, we found that:

38% had been placed on high intensity statin (10 patients on Atorvastatin 40 – 80mg, 3 patients on Rosuvastatin 20mg); 40% had been placed on moderate intensity statin (7 patients on Atorvastatin 10-20mg, 10 patients on Rosuvastatin 10mg, 1 patient on Pravastatin 40 mg); 6% on low intensity statin (2 patients on Pravastatin 10 mg); of the remaining patients 8% (n=3) were placed on Bempedioc and 8% (n=3) were on Ezetimide (with no other lipid lowering therapy). In total 28% (n=10) patients were on dual therapy with 11% taking Ezetimibe alongside a statin.

In the Community hub it was found that 31 people who finished the full clinic service, we found that: 23% had been placed on high intensity statin (7 patients on Atorvastatin 40 – 80mg); 61% had been placed on moderate intensity statin (17 patients on Atorvastatin 10-20mg, 1 patients

on Rosuvastatin 10mg, 1 patient on Simvastatin 40 mg); 6% on low intensity statin (2 patients on Pravastatin 10 mg); of the remaining patients 9% (n=3) were on Ezetimide (with no other lipid lowering therapy) and 3% (n=1) was placed on Evolocumab.

In the SBUHB GP clinic it was found that 19 people who finished the full clinic service, we found that: 53% had been placed on high intensity statin (10 patients on Atorvastatin 40 – 80mg);

37% had been placed on moderate intensity statin (6 patients on Atorvastatin 10-20mg, 1 patients on Rosuvastatin 10mg); 5% on low intensity statin (1 patients on Pravastatin 10 mg); the remaining patient 5% (n=1) were on Evolocumab. In total 26% (n=5) patients were on dual therapy with all taking Ezetimibe alongside a statin.

In the HDDUHB GP clinic it was found that 18 people who finished the full clinic service, we found that: 33% had been placed on high intensity statin (6 patients on Atorvastatin 40 – 80mg); 53% had been placed on moderate intensity statin (4 patients on Atorvastatin 10-20mg, 4 patients on Rosuvastatin 10mg, 1 patient on Simvastatin 40 mg); 6% on low intensity statin (1 patients on Pravastatin 10 mg); of the remaining patients 6% (n=1) were on Ezetimide (with no other lipid lowering therapy) and 6% (n=1) was placed on Evolocumab. In total 12% (n=2) patients were on dual therapy with 1 person taking Ezetimibe alongside a statin.

4.1.6 Point of Care Testing

A strong correlation was observed between point-of-care (PoC) lipid measurements and concurrent laboratory-based lipid profiles, indicating that PoC testing may serve as a reliable and efficient tool to guide lipid management decisions. This approach has the potential to streamline clinical workflows by reducing the need for additional phlebotomy appointments and pre-clinic laboratory confirmations, thereby minimising delays and optimising resource utilisation.

Figure 35. Total cholesterol results in matched samples of the POC analyser vs standard laboratory test.

Figure 36. LDL results in matched samples of the POC analyser vs standard laboratory test.

Figure 37. HDL results in matched samples of the POC analyser vs standard laboratory test.

Figure 38. Non HDL results in matched samples of the POC analyser vs standard laboratory test.

4.1.6.1 Bland Altman Plot

In addition to these tests Bland-Altman plots were created for each test (see figure 39,40,41 & 42). A Bland-Altman plot is used to visualize the differences in measurements between two different instruments or two different measurement techniques.[19]

It's useful for determining how similar two instruments or techniques are at measuring the same construct. The Bland Altman plots for each

test show good agreement between the standard laboratory tests and the POC tests (shown by a minimum of 95% of the results lying between 2 Standard deviations (shown by the upper and lower limits) of the average difference).

In addition, the results of all tests do not show any inherent bias in the measurements (shown by the relatively equal spread of the data between the limits) where neither the standard laboratory test nor the POC test have any particular bias in measurement.

Figure 39. Bland altman plot showing the agreement between the POC and standard laboratory test for total cholesterol.

Figure 40. Bland altman plot showing the agreement between the POC and standard laboratory test for LDL levels.

Figure 41. Bland altman plot showing the agreement between the POC and standard laboratory test for HDL levels.

Figure 42. Bland altman plot showing the agreement between the POC and standard laboratory test for non-HDL levels.

4.1.7 Weight Management

Although not a primary objective of the service, healthy lifestyle advice was routinely provided, and both weight and body mass index (BMI) were monitored during clinic visits.

Analysis of BMI data among patients who completed the full duration of the CVD prevention programme revealed a small but statistically significant reduction in BMI across all clinic sites (see figure 43).

This suggests that, in addition to pharmacological optimisation, the service may have contributed to modest improvements in lifestyle-related risk factors.

Overall change in BMI 31.1 ± 5.5 to 30.7 ± 5.4 kg/m² $p=0.048$
 Secondary care hub - 31.2 ± 5.1 to 30.8 ± 6.2 kg/m² $p=0.039^*$;
 Community hub - 30.5 ± 6.0 to 30.5 ± 6.4 kg/m² $p=0.9$;
 SBUHB GP clinic - 31.6 ± 6.0 to 30.7 ± 5.3 $p=0.081$;
 HDDUHB GP clinic - 31.4 ± 4.6 to 30.7 ± 4.5 $p=0.192$ However, the average BMI in all clinic settings remained > 30 kg/m² by visit 5. Of those who completed the service, 53% had a reduced BMI, 6% showed no change in BMI and 41% had an increased BMI.

Figure 43. BMI paired values for each patient at Visit 1 and Visit 5 for each of the different clinic models.

4.1.8 Quality of Life

To assess changes in health-related quality of life, the EQ-5D-5L patient-reported outcome measure (PROM) was administered at both Visit 1 and Visit 5. Analysis of the EQ-5D-5L index scores (see Figure 44) revealed that patients recruited into the secondary care hub and general practice (GP) clinics reported significantly lower baseline quality of life compared to those attending the community hub (mean index scores: 0.78 ± 0.16 and 0.80 ± 0.20 vs. 0.96 ± 0.05 , respectively; $p < 0.05$). Notably,

over 50% of patients in the community hub reported no problems across any EQ-5D-5L domains, yielding a perfect index score of 1.0.

These findings suggest potential discrepancies in patient characteristics across recruitment sites, despite the application of uniform eligibility criteria. Observed differences in baseline quality of life may reflect underlying variation in patient demographics and clinical complexity, with the secondary care hub cohort presenting with higher cardiovascular risk profiles and a greater burden of comorbidities.

Figure 44. Results of the Health Quality Index calculated from the EQ-5D-5L at visit 1 and 5 for the three clinic settings.

When analysing the change in health quality index value over the duration of their participation in the Clinic (change between visit 1 and visit 5) across all 3 clinics there is an observed (non-significant $p=0.186$) increase in general

quality of life (increase from 0.82 ± 0.23 to 0.85 ± 0.19). When analysing for the change at each of the three clinic settings (see figure 44). At the Community hub a significant ($p=0.043$) increase in health quality index is observed

(From 0.96±0.05 at visit 1 to 0.99±0.03 at visit 5) in addition a non-significant (p=0.104) increase is observed in the GP clinics (from 0.80±0.19 at visit 1 to 0.86±0.07 at visit 5). Conversely for the secondary care Hub there is no observable change in Health quality index (0.78±0.16 at Visit 1 and 0.78±0.15 at visit 5, p= 0.98).

Interestingly we observe 12 people in the secondary care hub and 9 people in the GP clinics who report decreased quality of life at visit 5. whilst this cannot all be attributed to the clinic as this is only a small part of the patients' lives as a whole; it is unexpected that improving people's health and reducing risk factors would be translate into a better quality of life.

In summary the results from the EQ-5D-5L and quality of life data suggest that there is perhaps some potential adjustments needed to the design of the clinics, whilst these clinics have proven to be effective in managing LDL and blood pressure there does not appear to be as

big an impact on quality of life. A key ingredient to prevention is improving peoples mental and physical wellbeing to ensure continued success.

In addition, as part of the EQ-5D-5L patients are asked to score their general health and wellbeing out of 100 (where a higher score indicates better health and wellbeing). This was measured at visit 1 and 2, the results can be seen in Table 7. The score shows varied results for the different clinic settings, no significant change is observed for the secondary care hub or GP clinics (although for the SBUHB GP clinic a non-significant reduction in a feeling of health and wellbeing is observed. This is in comparison to what is reported for the community hub which saw a significant (p=0.007) increase in the value reported (from 73.8 ± 15.1 to 78.6 ± 10.6) indicating a reported increase in wellbeing and health for this group of patients. This is supported by the significant increase observed in the health quality index (see above) for the community hub.

Figure 7. Table showing the average value of the self-reported health scale (out of 100) for the EQ-5D-5L for all patients who completed the prevention service.

	Visit 1		Visit 5		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Secondary Care Hub	73.5	16.9	75.1	16.1	0.5
Community Hub	73.8	15.1	78.6	10.6	0.007
GP Practices	74.7	17.1	72.7	21.4	0.7
SBUHB Clinic	75.7	17.7	71.6	21.8	0.3
HDDUHB Clinic	73.9	16.8	73.9	21.4	0.9

4.1.9 Staff and Patient Experience of the service

An integral component of this service evaluation involved capturing the perspectives of both patients and healthcare professionals engaged in the CVD prevention clinics. Data were collected through two primary methods.

First, patients who completed the programme were invited to complete an exit questionnaire, incorporating a validated patient-reported outcome measure (PROM) (see Appendix 3). Second, a series of semi-structured interviews

were conducted to explore key themes and reflections related to the service experience.

The qualitative component of the evaluation employed a reflexive thematic analysis approach, guided by Braun and Clarke's (2022) six-phase methodology.[20]

This multisite evaluation aimed to elicit in-depth insights into the experiences of service users and providers, as well as to assess the perceived health impact of the CVD prevention service across different clinical settings.

4.1.9.1 Patient Experience: Findings from the Patient Exit Interview

4.1.9.1.1 Patient's Reflexive Thematic Analysis

Figure 45. Visual Representation of AMGEN Patient Final Reflexive Thematic Themes and associated Sub – Themes.

A total of six final reflexive thematic themes were identified for professionals: 1) Felt Heard, Respected, and Supported; 2) Picked Up on What Was Missed; 3) The Right Treatment at the Right Time; 4) It Made Me Stop and Think; 5) More People Should Have This; 6) Well Run, but Could Be Even Better. These final themes are visually represented and discussed in detail above (figure 45).

4.1.9.1.2 Patient Theme 1: Felt Heard, Respected, and Supported

Participants valued the service's human touch - time, empathy, and being treated as individuals. Many compared it positively to GP experiences, where interactions felt rushed.

"They listened to everything I said. I didn't feel rushed like at the GP's - it felt like they actually cared" (P5, Ceredigion).

The care model stood out for its consistency and patient-centred approach.

"You're not seen as just a number. They took really good care of me and spent time explaining everything" (P6, Ceredigion).

These positive experiences helped build trust and encouraged participants to engage

more openly with advice. The ability to ask questions without judgment created a safe space, especially for sensitive topics like weight, medication, and lifestyle.

Emotional support wasn't just a benefit - it enabled better follow-through. Participants felt encouraged, not lectured, and many left feeling more confident in managing their health. The strong relational dynamic contributed to the success of the service. As it scales, retaining this person-centred ethos will be key. The findings reinforce that how people are treated - not just what they're told - shapes their willingness to act and their satisfaction with care.

4.1.9.1.3 Patient theme 2: Picked Up on What Was Missed

Participants often described the service as something that uncovered health issues their usual care missed.

"I found out my cholesterol was high. I wouldn't have known otherwise - nobody else picked that up".

This early detection wasn't just about data - it offered reassurance and direction.

“They took blood tests my doctor never arranged and caught things early. That made a big difference”.

Many participants expressed relief at having hidden problems identified and addressed. Some felt validated, especially if they had longstanding concerns. Others appreciated the clarity the service provided after years of vague feedback. Discovering health issues early also triggered action - whether lifestyle changes or medication reviews - and reinforced the value of proactive care. This theme highlights the service’s ability to bridge a gap in routine practice. Rather than reacting to symptoms, the model offered early, data-informed interventions. This felt empowering for patients, who saw the service as a form of prevention rather than crisis response. By detecting issues that might otherwise be missed, the service positioned itself as both clinically effective and personally meaningful.

4.1.9.1.4 Patient Theme 3: The Right Treatment at the Right Time

Medication reviews and treatment adjustments were widely praised. Many participants had not had this level of individualised input before.

“They changed my medication twice until they found what worked. That helped me a lot”.

Others felt reassured by new prescriptions or clearer explanations.

“My blood pressure tablets were reviewed and adjusted. I feel more stable now”.

These conversations helped participants better understand their treatment, reduced anxiety, and built trust.

They valued the sense that staff were tailoring advice to their specific needs rather than just following a script. For those managing chronic conditions, the practical impact was significant - from better stability to fewer side effects. This personalised approach helped participants feel more in control. Importantly, it showed that reviewing prescriptions wasn’t about “fixing mistakes,” but optimising care. The careful, responsive style of these reviews reflected a service that listened and adapted - not just applied general rules. This theme underscores the role of collaborative decision-making in treatment

adherence and satisfaction. The process of jointly reviewing and modifying treatment plans helped people feel not just treated but genuinely cared for.

4.1.9.1.5 Patient Theme 4: It Made Me Stop and Think

The service often prompted reflection, helping participants reconsider daily habits and health priorities.

“It made me more aware of what I eat -I even started counting calories with my wife”.

This wasn’t just about new information - it was about rethinking personal responsibility.

“You start thinking about your health more. It’s always on the back burner, but they brought it to the front”

The sense that someone was “keeping an eye” on them fostered accountability. But rather than feeling monitored, participants felt supported. Many described small but meaningful shifts - from increased physical activity to better food choices. Some used digital tools like step counters, others changed routines with their families. The service wasn’t about quick fixes; it invited slow, sustainable behaviour change. The supportive tone - rather than judgement - encouraged people to act on the advice in their own time. In short, the service didn’t just offer advice. It helped people pause, reflect, and reset their thinking. This mindset shift, more than any single intervention, may be one of the service’s most powerful long-term contributions to health improvement.

4.1.9.1.6 Patient Theme 5: More People Should Have This

Participants weren’t just satisfied - they became advocates. They wanted others to benefit too.

“Absolutely -it’s helpful for everyone, not just high-risk people. Even young folks should do it”.

Several said they had already recommended it to relatives.

“It’s something that should be done for all preventable health issues. I’ve told my kids about it too”.

They saw the service as addressing a gap in GP care - offering time, prevention, and meaningful

follow-up that many felt was missing. Importantly, this advocacy was rooted in trust. Participants saw tangible outcomes and wanted that extended to others. Equity emerged as a strong subtext. Many spoke about people in rural areas, underserved groups, or those who rarely visit doctors. The idea that this kind of proactive, approachable service could reach them mattered deeply. This theme shows that the service didn’t just treat individuals - it built social momentum. Participants wanted their communities to share in something they found transformative. The model clearly struck a chord, and that resonance suggests strong potential for scale, if the quality can be maintained.

4.1.9.1.7 Patient theme 6: Well Run, but Could Be Even Better

While participants praised the service’s delivery, several had thoughtful suggestions. Most feedback focused on continuity, information access, and self-monitoring tools.

“Everything worked well, but I’d have liked a printout or maybe a chart to keep track of my bloods”.

“It was great overall, but a small group session or some follow-up would really help reinforce the advice”.

Rather than complaints, these were practical ideas for enhancing the experience. Participants appreciated the structure, but some wanted visual aids, clearer data summaries, or more structured follow-up appointments. Others suggested support groups or digital tools to help continue progress at home. Accessibility was also mentioned - both logistical (e.g., transport and location) and emotional (e.g., knowing whom to contact after). A few highlighted that older adults or those unfamiliar with tech might need extra support. These insights reinforce that the service was effective, but that success brings expectations. Participants cared enough to offer solutions, not just praise. Integrating their suggestions could help future iterations of the service become more sustainable, more inclusive, and even more impactful.

4.1.9.1.8 Positive Outcomes - Patients

“Because it helps people make an informed choice about what they’re doing. And it gives people time to speak to the qualified people.”

“Just knowing that somebody was actually there, so like keeping an eye on things... it’s motivation as well, isn’t it?... It just made you feel a bit more yeah. Somebody is trying as well as me.”

“I just find it informative, and I’ve addressed it positively... I’m quite happy.”

4.1.9.1.9 Quotes from patients

“Just more availability to people... make it available to everyone. Yeah. I guess with some sort of screening... you won’t know nothing about it, if anything.”

“The first gentleman I saw was slightly antagonistic and uncomfortable... What came across to me was a very directive approach to telling people what they should be doing... is counterproductive.”

“For laypeople... it is quite a nervous situation... it’s quite easy for general public to feel slightly intimidated... we should never underestimate the value of simple encouragement.”

4.1.9.2 Staff Experience

4.1.9.2.1 Staff Reflexive Thematic Analysis

A total of four final reflexive thematic themes were identified for professionals: 1) Empowered Patients Through Clarity and Connection; 2) Prevention in Action: Holistic, Accessible, and Patient-Centred; 3) Innovation Undermined by Fragmented Systems; 4) Professionals Driving Change with Purpose and Pride. These final themes are presented visually, and discussed in detail, below (figure 46).

Figure 46. Visual Representation of Professionals' Reflexive Thematic Analytic Sub – Themes and Final Themes.

4.1.9.2.2 Staff Theme 1: Empowered Patients Through Clarity and Connection

Participants consistently highlighted how the service created an environment that encouraged patient understanding and agency. This was not only about providing information but also about how that information was delivered - through calm, respectful, and attentive communication. Patients were given the space to express concerns, ask questions, and engage in a meaningful dialogue about their health.

“People went away with knowledge.”

Locum Consultant Acute Physician at Hywel Dda (UHB)

This empowerment was especially notable in cases involving higher-risk individuals, where preventive discussions often marked a turning point. Staff noted that the informal, supportive tone allowed patients to drop their guard and genuinely engage with new health information. Furthermore, structured follow-up and continuity of care helped reinforce messages and encourage accountability.

“Patients felt looked after.”

Clinical Research Nurse, Hywel Dda (UHB)

These findings suggest that trust-building and emotional support are critical elements in facilitating informed decision-making. The environment and approach of the service enabled patients to become more than passive recipients - they became participants in their own health journey.

4.1.9.2.3 Staff Theme 2: Prevention in Action: Holistic, Accessible, and Patient-Centered

The emphasis on prevention was seen as one of the most transformative elements of the service. By combining accessible locations with extended, person-centered consultations, the service encouraged meaningful engagement around health behaviours. Staff described these sessions as distinct from typical appointments - more relaxed, more comprehensive, and more focused on patient narratives.

“Patients had time to reflect.”

Locum Consultant Acute Physician at Hywel Dda (UHB)

Participants reported that the environment, particularly the ability to park easily and enter a non-hospital space, made a noticeable difference. Patients arrived calmer and more receptive. Moreover, the model’s design ensured they had enough time with healthcare professionals to delve into personal histories and risk factors - something rarely possible in standard clinical settings.

“Single point for patients.”

Clinical Research Specialist Nurse, at Hywel Dda (UHB)

Ultimately, this theme illustrates that a well-designed preventive care model - grounded in accessibility, time, and empathy - can significantly increase engagement and enable behavioural change. It reaffirms the idea that how care is delivered is just as important as what is delivered.

4.1.9.2.4 Staff Theme 3: Innovation Undermined by Fragmented Systems

Despite the project’s promise, operational inefficiencies repeatedly emerged as barriers to its full impact. Participants across multiple roles highlighted significant issues with system compatibility, data retrieval, and scheduling clarity. These problems not only delayed implementation but often left staff frustrated and overburdened.

“Vision system no longer viable.”

Pharmacist, Hywel Dda (UHB)

IT and infrastructure constraints disrupted the - patient journey and led to uneven experiences across sites. Inconsistent processes - such as referral systems and unclear ownership of appointment workflows - meant that the quality of service varied depending on location and team. Many staff members reported having to ‘work around the system’ to ensure patient needs were met.

“Getting data was painful.”

Lead Pharmacist for Cardiac Services, Hywel Dda (UHB)

This theme underscores a recurring truth in service innovation: even the most human-centered models can be stalled by outdated infrastructure. The need for unified platforms, standardized procedures, and integrated digital tools was voiced repeatedly as key to sustainability and scale-up.

4.1.9.2.5 Staff Theme 4: Professionals Driving Change with Purpose and Pride

A consistent thread through all transcripts was the enthusiasm and commitment of staff expressed toward the service. Many described the work as refreshing - something that reignited their passion for patient care and innovation. This was particularly true for those involved in the early design or pilot phases.

“We had to build this service from the ground up.”

Lead Pharmacist for Cardiac Services at Hywel Dda (UHB)

Collaboration emerged as a core enabler of this energy. Whether it was interdisciplinary teamwork or joint problem-solving across practices, staff spoke positively about the relationships formed and the autonomy they were given. They felt seen, trusted, and integral to the project’s success.

“Delighted to be involved.”

Locum Consultant Acute Physician at Hywel Dda University Health Board (UHB)

Beyond professional fulfilment, this pride translated into tangible benefits for the service. Staff went above and beyond their roles, took initiative, and adapted quickly to challenges. Their drive became a key pillar of implementation success, illustrating how staff engagement is central to innovation in care delivery.

4.1.9.2.6 Positive Outcomes - Quotes from Professionals

“The majority of patients have been really engaged, and they’ve got something from it... it’s been quite nice to see the whole journey.”

Clinical Research Unit

“It’s excellent... it really has the opportunity to engage with and educate patients on their risk factors for cardiovascular disease.”

Clinical Research Nurse

“There’s some surprise things coming out of it – one [was] how receptive the wider community was... and how open people were to MDT working... and giving up their time.”

Lead Pharmacist, Cardiac Services

“We had the time to look at all aspects of their lifestyle... it’s not the typical 10-15 minutes at a GP surgery... a lot of patients enjoyed that.”

Lead Pharmacist, Cardiac Services

4.1.9.2.7 Challenges & Barriers - Quotes from Professionals

“To do the search, it took us about 3 or 4 hours... each factor separately... if you got something wrong at the first step... you have to start again. So, it did take ages.”

Advisory Pharmacist

“There was lots of confusion around... getting approvals from the primary care teams... lots of issues around data, information governance... the DCHW team didn’t really talk to our local IG team.”

Deputy Head of Innovation

“There was a lot of problems in the beginning... agreements between the people setting up and the GP surgeries... and it had to go through digital services. That was really frustrating.”

Clinical Research Nurse

4.1.10 Summary of the clinical Effectiveness

A key indicator of success for the CVD prevention clinics was the proportion of patients who completed the full 12-month review period. The overall retention rate was 69%, with a dropout rate of 31%. While the loss of approximately one-third of participants may appear substantial, this figure is considered acceptable given the intensity and time commitment required, up to 52 weeks of engagement, including six scheduled clinic visits. Compared to typical dropout rates observed in similar long-term clinical services, this retention rate reflects a relatively high level of sustained patient engagement.

Clinical effectiveness outcomes demonstrated several benefits across all service settings, confirming the programme's impact in managing cardiovascular risk. The primary objective of the clinics was to optimise blood pressure and lipid control in individuals at moderate to high risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD). Among patients who completed the programme, a statistically significant reduction in low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) was observed, with an average decrease of 1.0 mmol/L ($p < 0.001$). Furthermore, 37% of these patients achieved the recommended LDL-C target of ≤ 1.8 mmol/L, which is associated with a meaningful reduction in estimated 10-year CVD risk.

An additional positive outcome was the successful implementation of point-of-care (PoC) lipid testing. Comparative analysis between PoC results and paired laboratory samples revealed strong positive correlations and Bland-Altman plots show strong agreement between the test. These findings suggest that PoC testing may serve as a reliable alternative to laboratory-based lipid profiling, provided that robust quality control procedures and appropriate reagent storage protocols are maintained. The use of PoC testing could streamline the clinical pathway by reducing the need for pre-screening visits (e.g., Visit 1A) and enabling real-time decision-making based on up-to-date lipid measurements obtained during the clinic appointment.

The other primary goal of the clinic was to manage and control Blood pressure to below 140(systolic) /90 (diastolic). Whilst it was found that for most patients BP readings (particularly the systolic reading) fluctuated during their different clinic visits, when comparing the systolic BP readings at visit 1 and visit 5 for patients a significant reduction ($p < 0.0001$) was observed proving that the clinic was particularly effective in reducing blood pressure and miniating it at a level below the risk threshold. As systolic BP was found to be below 140 in approximately 80% of people who completed the service. The clinics were not a complete success as we observed for 26 patients (around 23% of all the patients who finished the clinic) systolic blood pressure levels either did not change, increased or were still above the threshold value of 140mmHg.

When comparing the demographics of the patients recruited into the different clinic types or into the different health boards several differences were observed. This is a potential weakness of any comparison between the different clinics. Although the key indicator for success for the prevention clinic was each individuals reduction in LDL and BP which would be largely independent of the patients comorbidities.

It is important to recognise that this is a quality improvement (service evaluation) piece of work and was not designed to directly compare the different service models but rather to look at the effectiveness or a CVD prevention clinic. The different clinic settings were designed to tackle the very different challenges that the geography in South and West Wales. Phase 2 was not a research study, it was a real-world evaluation of CVD prevention clinics and so patients were selected on a biggest need or first come first served basis. The key limitations and observations were:

- The SBUHB clinics had higher proportions of people with higher risk and more comorbidities. In addition, they had a significantly higher proportion of secondary care patients enrolled in the service. This meant that the patients in the SBUHB sites could be viewed as more 'ill' or 'sick' and generally had more complicated medical histories, this was seen by the far larger proportion of patients who were referred into other specialist secondary care clinics

from the SBUHB clinics. This is also reflected in the Quality of life (PROM) data collected.

- Another weakness of the data collected is that some of the data collected is self-reported by the patients (through the general lifestyle questionnaire). When reviewing the self-reported information against data collected from the patients notes there were several cases of discrepancy between the two. In most of these cases where possible the data from the medical notes was used. In addition, some of the data is purely self-reported such as smoking status and level of exercise, there are concerns that some of this data may either be under reported (smoking) or over reported (exercise level), particularly due to the high level of other risk factors such as obesity.

Despite the limitations the demographics data has shown the recruitment process to be largely successful. The correct types of patients were recruited into the service, with patients across all three clinic models showing high risk of CVD, high levels of obesity, high proportion of smokers, high levels of hyperlipemia, diabetes and hypertension.

Despite the differences in patient demographics there were no discernible differences between the effectiveness of the different clinic models, at least not in terms of reduction in LDL and blood pressure readings for the individuals. It was also found that the clinics had no noticeable effect on patients living healthier or happy lives. There was no significant improvement in weight loss or in patients reported quality of life or any reliable data on smoking cessation rates. In summary this data suggests that there are perhaps some potential adjustments needed to the design of the clinics, whilst ten clinics have proven to be effective in managing LDL and blood pressure there does not appear to be as big an impact on quality of life. A key ingredient to prevention is improving peoples mental and physical wellbeing to ensure continued success.

The combined analysis of patient and professional interviews reveals a coherent, mutually reinforcing picture of a cardiovascular service that is not only well-received but genuinely impactful. Patients described feeling heard, respected, and supported – in sharp contrast to the transactional nature of typical GP consultations. They praised the service for uncovering hidden health risks,

improving medication understanding, and motivating sustainable lifestyle changes. Equally, professionals reflected a deep sense of purpose and pride in delivering a preventive model of care that filled gaps in routine practice. Both groups acknowledged strong relational dynamics, citing continuity, empathy, and the time to talk as key enablers of engagement. Challenges were also acknowledged, particularly around systemic and technical barriers, such as fragmented IT systems, limited access to follow-up resources, and the need for improved infrastructure if the model is to scale effectively. Yet across both datasets, the tone was hopeful, constructive, and future focused. Participants didn't just endorse the service, they wanted more of it, for more people. This evaluation highlights that with the right structure, ethos, and attention to continuity, a preventive cardiovascular service can be both clinically effective and emotionally resonant. The findings offer a strong foundation for refinement, scale-up, and continued investment in relational, proactive models of care.

4.2 Cost assessment

4.2.1 Cost of the CVD prevention Service and potential benefit

In estimating the cost of delivering the CVD prevention service per patient, several key factors must be considered. The service model is resource-intensive, characterised by frequent patient contact, multiple clinical assessments, and multidisciplinary input. As designed, the pathway includes up to six face-to-face clinic visits over a 52-week period. The initial visit is nurse-led, while subsequent visits are led by a specialist pharmacist with nursing support. In addition to these in-person appointments, four telephone follow-up consultations are conducted by the nursing team between Visits 2 and 5.

The service is further supported by consultant cardiologists who participate in regular multidisciplinary team (MDT) meetings with pharmacists to review complex cases and guide medication adjustments. Additional cost considerations include laboratory investigations (e.g., lipid profiles), point-of-care testing, and routine clinical assessments such as blood pressure and weight monitoring, conducted during Visits 1, 3, 4, and 5.

For community hub and GP-based clinics, staff travel costs must also be factored into the overall service delivery expenditure. These cumulative elements contribute to a comprehensive, yet resource-demanding, model of care aimed at optimising cardiovascular risk management in high-risk populations.

Current estimated Costs per patient for the Secondary Care Hub

- Staff costs to deliver the clinic for one patient assuming the patient completes the full clinic is between £1,220, (taking consultation process, time to undertake all assessments and review, consumable and admin costs)

Current estimated Costs per patient for the Community Hub

- Staff costs to deliver the clinic for one patient assuming the patient completes the full clinic is between £1,326, (taking consultation process, time to undertake all assessments and review, consumable and admin costs, INCLUDING ESTIMATED TRAVEL COSTS)

Current estimated Costs per patient for the GP Clinics

- Staff costs to deliver the clinic for one patient assuming the patient completes the full clinic is between £1,446 (taking consultation process, time to undertake all assessments and review, consumable and admin costs, INCLUDING ESTIMATED TRAVEL COSTS)

The clinical effectiveness of the service has shown to be effective in reducing LDL levels and especially effective for 36% of patients who completed the service having an LDL below 1.8mmol/L at the end of the service. In addition, the clinics proved effective in managing Blood Pressure with 81% or all people who completed the service showing a blood pressure below 140/90. The significance of this finding is that the CVD prevention clinic has the potential to reduce the 10-year risk for patients who complete the service in terms of their total LDL from 3.15 mmol/L (SD 0.83) for visit 1 to 2.18 mmol/L (SD 0.86). Taking the fact that major ASCVD events is

likely to be 21% lower and the relative risk of death 10% lower per 1mol/L reduction in LDL-cholesterol. This translates as a potential

relative risk reduction in a major ASCVD events by 20% due to the CVD prevention clinics IF the reduction in LDL levels holds true for all patients.

4.2.2 Evaluation of the Cost-effectiveness of different cardiovascular disease risk management models in Wales

4.2.2.1 Model type and structure

A decision analytic model was developed using TreeAge Pro Healthcare 2025 to compare the four alternatives i.e. three new delivery care models in addition to Care-as-usual (CAU) in accordance to current clinical guidelines [9,21-23] vs CAU alone) in terms of costs and quality adjusted life years (QALYs) over patients' lifetime. The model consisted of a decision tree followed by a patient cohort Markov Model. The branches in the decision tree modelled separately individuals with or without CAD at three risk categories i.e. low/medium, high and very-high risk category. The subsequent nodes following the risk classification corresponded to the management of patients with statins. The treatment effects of the three new delivery models were modelled in the decision tree as the changed management in statins compared to the statin management following CAU. As such, the last nodes of the branches in the new models, were either statin initiation, increase statin dose, or CAU (i.e. statin management did not change with a new delivery model).

Following the decision tree, individuals entered a Markov model health state including: no obstructive CAD (no CAD), MI, stroke, heart failure, CAD, cardiac death, and other death. The initial health state for individuals without existing CAD was no CAD. For individuals with existing CAD, the no CAD health state was dropped from the Markov model and the initial health state for these individuals was CAD.

The Markov model had a cycle of three months (i.e. individuals could stay in the same health state or transit to other health states every three months) and a time horizon of lifetime (i.e. 30 years). The structure of the Markov model is illustrated in Figure 43. The economic evaluation was then performed over a lifetime time horizon. This was conducted using the NHS costing perspective, and a discount rate of 3.5% was used for both costs and outcomes.

Figure 47. Markov model illustrating transition of health state every 3 months cycle.

4.2.2.2 Model parameters: Real-world risk-reclassification evaluation study

For this analysis model 1 is of the secondary care hub clinic, Model 2 is of the community hub clinic and model 3 is for a generic single GP site clinic

4.2.2.2.1 Meta-analysis on the effect size of statin treatment on cardiovascular event rates

The treatment effect of statin therapy on MACE was informed by the largest published meta-analysis (data from 170,000 participants in 26 randomised trials, Cholesterol Treatment Trialists' (CTT) Collaboration).[24] The percentage reduction in LDL cholesterol (mmol/l) was 48% with 40mg of Atorvastatin and 53% with 80mg Atorvastatin.[25] Using a 3.7mmol/l baseline LDL cholesterol,[26] we calculated the relative risk of having MACE when statin (Atorvastatin) was initiated (i.e.. from 0mg to 40mg) and intensified (i.e. from 40mg to 80 mg) by CAD status and different baseline risk level.

4.2.2.2.2 Healthcare cost and utility measures

The costs in each health state were derived from three UK studies and included resource use in primary and secondary care.[27-29] All costs were inflated from their base year to 2024 values using the Hospital and Community Health Service (HCHS) pay and price inflation. The cost of statin treatment (i.e. 40mg and 80mg of atorvastatin)

was derived from the British National Formulary and applied to patients' lifetime once it had been initiated. For each health state, a utility score was assigned based on the most recent UK based literature.[30] For cardiac mortality and other death health states the utility score was set to 0. QALYs were calculated by applying the area-under-the-curve method. The cost of each of the three new delivery models were £1,220, £1,326, and £1,446 for Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3 respectively.

4.2.2.2.3 Transition probabilities

The transition probabilities between the different health states were informed by [31].

4.2.2.3 Sensitivity analyses

Finally, to express the uncertainty around the estimated incremental cost effectiveness ratio (ICER), a probabilistic sensitivity analysis was performed by sampling 1,000 sets of input parameters from their pre-specified distributions resulting in 1,000 pairs of estimated incremental costs and incremental outcomes. These simulated ICERs were plotted on cost-effectiveness planes to display uncertainty in the estimated ICER. In addition, cost-effectiveness acceptability curve (CEAC) was drawn to display the probability of each intervention to be cost-effective at different levels of ceiling ratio (i.e. different values of a QALY).

4.2.2.4 Results of the cost evaluation

The cost-utility analysis revealed that implementing new delivery Model 1 in clinical care is highly cost-effective with lifetime ICER/QALY of £3,087 compared to care as Usual (Table 8). The other two new delivery models (I.e. Model 2 and Model 3) were dominated by Model 1 as the costed more and generated less QALYs than Model 1.

The dominance of Model 1 over Model 2 and Model 3 are graphically illustrated in Figure 44 where, Models 2 & 3 are well behind the cost-effectiveness frontier. the dominance of this model over the others is primarily due to the 'no travel' expenses in the cost of the secondary care hub due to staff being located at their 'primary workplace) in a secondary care clinic with no need to travel offsite.

The travel expenses for staff for the community hub clinic model has been calculated on average

miles travelled by staff from the primary base to the location of the community care hub clinic location. The travel expenses for the GP clinic have been calculated for the furthest travel distances required to attend the Clinic at the GP location. The uncertainty around the ICER is presented in the cost-effectiveness acceptability curve (Figure 45) where all 1,000 simulated ICERs were well below the ceiling ratio of £20,000/QALY. The probability of the Model 1 of being cost-effective was 1 at a threshold value lower than £5,000, which is well below the £20,000/QALY threshold recommended by NICE.

This evaluation has demonstrated that new delivery Model 1 that reclassifies patients and changes management by improving the accuracy of risk prediction in primary and secondary CVD prevention is highly cost-effective compared with care as usual.

The deployment of this model in clinical practice would be cost-effective, to refine risk assessment,

guide additional treatments and prevent major adverse cardiovascular events and death.

Table 8. Results of the cost-utility analysis.

	Costs Mean (95%CI)	QALYS Mean (95%CI)	Incremental costs Mean (95%CI)	Incremental QALYS Mean (95%CI)	ICER Point estimate (95%CI)
Usual Care	£7,833 (7,174-8,484)	12.84 (11.78-13.64)			
Model 1	£9,037 (8,339-9,690)	13.23 (12.14-14.07)	£1,204 (1,016-1,358)	0.39 (0.34-0.42)	£3,087 (2,542-3,669)
Model 2	£9,045 (8,347- 9,697)	13.17 (12.09-14.01)	£8 (-0.18-16)	-0.06 (-0.08 -0.03)	Dominated
Model 3	£9,047 (8,351-9,697)	13.09 (12.02-13.93)	£10 (0.38-20.20)	-0.14 (-0.16 -0.10)	Dominated

Notes: CI: confidence interval; ICER: incremental cost-effectiveness ratio; QALY: quality-adjusted life year.

Figure 48. Cost-effectiveness frontier.

Figure 49. Cost-effectiveness acceptability curve.

4.3 Barriers to implementation

A critical component of evaluating any quality improvement initiative involves identifying the barriers and limitations encountered during implementation. The establishment of the CVD prevention clinics was no exception, with several recurring challenges observed across both Hywel Dda University Health Board (HDDUHB) and Swansea Bay University Health Board (SBUHB). It is reasonable to infer that these challenges are not unique to the participating sites and may be generalisable to other health boards across Wales and potentially to similar healthcare systems elsewhere.

In addition to the barriers and limitations identified through qualitative analysis of staff and patient feedback, several key operational and systemic challenges were noted, including:

4.3.1 Poor Primary Care Engagement

One of the key barriers encountered across both health boards was the challenge of navigating the primary care infrastructure. While initial engagement with GP practices was positive, translating expressions of interest into sustained collaboration often proved difficult and time-consuming. In several cases, follow-up with interested practices led to dead ends or last-minute withdrawals. For example, one GP practice initially agreed to participate but, after three months of repeated requests, failed to send out any referral letters and ceased responding to communications. This ultimately led to the practice being removed from the programme and replaced, causing delays in patient recruitment.

At Swansea Bay UHB sites, additional complications arose due to information governance protocols between the clinic team and GP practices. All patient searches and invitation letters had to be initiated by the GP surgeries themselves. This dependency led to significant delays, as agreed timelines for these tasks were frequently missed by the practices.

These experiences raise important concerns about the feasibility of a GP practice-led model for CVD prevention clinics. If this model were to be adopted more widely, it would require consistent and proactive collaboration from the majority, or ideally all GP practices within a region. Achieving

this level of coordination would likely necessitate a health board-wide agreement and a formal mandate at the highest level to ensure alignment and commitment across primary care partners.

4.3.2 Limited Space to Hold the Clinics

A significant challenge encountered by Hywel Dda UHB was the lack of available space within GP practices to host the CVD prevention clinics. This issue was common across many practices, which struggled to allocate both time and physical space within their premises. As a result, the number of practices able to participate in the service was limited. This raises important concerns about the viability of delivering the clinics solely within GP settings, particularly if the service were to be scaled across the entire health board. Without sufficient space, some segments of the patient population may be excluded from accessing the service. Moreover, addressing space constraints within individual practices is not a straightforward task and may not be easily resolved.

In addition, Hywel Dda UHB initially faced difficulties in identifying a suitable facility to serve as a primary care hub. This issue was eventually resolved in March 2023, when a site in Ceredigion was secured. However, this experience highlights the potential logistical challenges of establishing multiple community hub locations to ensure equitable coverage across a geographically dispersed region like Hywel Dda UHB.

4.3.3 Difficulties around Information Governance

Data governance emerged as a key challenge, particularly given that this service, while delivered in the community, is fundamentally a secondary care initiative. It relies heavily on secondary care teams accessing primary care facilities and patient data, especially in the Hywel Dda UHB region. Unlike Swansea Bay UHB, Hywel Dda adopted a different operational model, whereby the service team conducted patient searches and issued invitation letters directly. This approach was intended to mitigate the delays experienced in the SBUHB model, where such tasks were dependent on GP practices.

In Wales, information governance for primary care is overseen by Digital Health and Care Wales (DHCW). The HDDUHB team encountered several issues and miscommunications between its internal IG team and DHCW, resulting in a four-month delay to the start of patient recruitment (see Hywel Dda Patient Recruitment Summary). This delay had a significant impact on project momentum, necessitating renewed engagement and reassurance efforts with participating GP practices.

4.3.4 Point of Care Barrier

Another significant barrier encountered during the study was the use of point-of-care (POC) analysers. The Cholestech LDX device was assessed for measuring lipid profiles as a comparator to routine laboratory testing. The original plan was to collect POC samples at the point of recruitment; however, a number of cassettes and reagents delivered for the device had a short shelf life. Upon reordering, the manufacturer and supplier (Abbott) had no stock available within the UK, resulting in an eight-week delay in obtaining new supplies. Consequently, the device could not be used during the initial recruitment phase.

Once supplies were replenished, POC testing was carried out when feasible—typically alongside laboratory blood draws. However, additional logistical issues arose at remote locations, such as GP surgeries and community hubs within Hywel Dda UHB. These sites often lacked adequate refrigerated storage space for reagents, which led to unusable samples and insufficient stock to complete all planned tests.

4.4 Phase 2: Limitations, Conclusions and Value Assessment.

4.4.1 Limitations

The outcomes of Phase 2 of the project have revealed a number of barriers and limitations. These are summarised below.

Data access, data Integrity & Recruitment Barriers

- Inconsistent patient identification protocols in the different health boards led to some delays to the timelines of the project. This particularly impacted SBUHB, where clinics relied on GP-led identification and contact of patients for referral into the CVD prevention clinic As a

result when the GPs were busy this resulted in delayed posting of invitation letters etc which led to 4-5 month delay in recruitment.

- Conversely while the HDDUHB site did not have these problems due to the clinic team being responsible for identification this did cause several issue with Data access and information governance. This issues with access to data caused approximately a 5-6month delay in starting the project at HDDUHB.

Operational Constraints

- Space limitations in GP practices restricted service scalability, this meant that several GPs that were approached turned down the offer of inclusion into the program as they 'lacked' space. For future rollout this is a serious consideration.
- POC testing was delayed due to supply and storage constraints.
- IT systems were fragmented and poorly integrated, leading to inefficiencies in data retrieval and patient tracking.

Service Design Disparity

- Demographic variation between clinic settings (e.g., SBUHB sites had higher risk and comorbidities). As a result this could have led to some limitations when comparing the different clinic models. However, it is worthwhile to note that the key indicator is the change in each individual particularly reduction in BP and LDL, which was largely unaffected by the difference in the patient demographics in the 3 settings.

Limited Broader Impact

- Minimal change in overall BMI and inconsistent improvement in reported quality of life. This is somewhat expected as the driving focus in the design of the service was around BP and LDL management. In future iterations of the CVD prevention clinics some additional thought may be required around general lifestyle improvement and management.
- Emotional and psychological wellbeing impacts varied, particularly in higher-risk populations.

4.4.2 Conclusions

Phase 2 has led to several important findings and conclusions:

Clinical Effectiveness

- The CVD prevention clinics have proved to be clinically effective, particularly in their key objective of reducing BL and LDL. This is primarily due to the design of the clinics which focused on medication management and reduction of these two key variables.
- The clinics demonstrated strong effectiveness in reducing LDL-C (mean reduction ~0.9–1.18 mmol/L) and systolic blood pressure (mean reduction ~16–30 mmHg).
- 81% of patients achieved BP control (<140/90 mmHg); 37% achieved LDL-C ≤1.8 mmol/L.
- POC lipid testing showed strong agreement with lab-based testing, supporting future and further integration in any future services based off this programme. The POC test could be used to streamline the current pathway that has been designed.

Patient Engagement

- 69% of patients completed the full 12-month service, an encouraging retention rate for a long-term, intensive programme.
- Patients reported feeling supported, respected, and engaged, with many crediting the service for motivating lifestyle changes and uncovering undiagnosed issues.
- Patients identified that they felt the service cared for them and was picking up issues that were missing in the current standard of care. Patients felt that the service was a form of prevention rather than a response to a crisis or issue. Patients felt the service was optimising their care and made the patients reflect on their daily habits and responsibilities.
- A key comment was that patients felt more people should have access to the service.

Professional Reflections

- Staff saw the model as holistic, meaningful, and empowering for patients, but faced frustrations with governance, systems, and infrastructure.
- Staff identified that they felt empowered and enjoyed the working within the clinics, feeling like they were making difference.

Clinic Model Comparison

- All three models (secondary care hub, community hub, GP practice) were clinically effective. This was expected as a strict service protocol was implemented across all three service models. Each patient recruited into the service received very similar care independent of the clinic site. The major differences occurred outside of the actual delivery of the service and were caused by governance, systems, and infrastructure issues.

4.4.3 Value Assessment

An important element of this work is to understand the value and affordability of a CVD prevention clinic. Whilst any value or cost/affordability assessment is limited at this stage due to the design and size of the pilot phase 2 quality improvement work. Initial findings show:

Cost-Effectiveness

- Model 1 (secondary care hub) yielded an ICER of £3,087/QALY, well below the NICE threshold of £20,000.
- Models 2 (community hub) and 3 (GP practice) were more costly and yielded fewer QALYs, thus were dominated in the cost-utility analysis.

Economic Impact

- Model 1 showed strong lifetime value with fewer logistical costs (e.g. no staff travel) and better infrastructure support.
- Estimated per-patient delivery costs ranged from £1,220 (Model 1-Secondary care hub) to £1,448 (Model 3- GP practice clinics), with substantial clinical benefits in LDL-C and BP reduction.

Health Outcomes

- The data demonstrates that targeted intervention, by a ring-fenced resource that doesn't succumb to the acute pressures within the existing system is likely to provide significant improvement in patient outcomes.
- The programme has the potential to reduce 10-year CVD risk by ~20% through sustained lipid and BP management, potentially preventing major adverse events.

5 Recommendations

1. Supported by Phase 3 Work: Scale-Up the Different Care Models

Recommendation Expansion:

- Prioritise the new models of care: Leverage the evidence from Phase 3 to scale the different models, which have demonstrated superior cost-effectiveness, infrastructure efficiency, and QALY gains. This model should serve as the blueprint for regional hubs, particularly in areas with high ASCVD prevalence.
- Embed within Regional Planning: Align the expansion with regional cardiovascular networks and cluster-level planning to ensure equitable access and reduce unwarranted variation.
- Develop Workforce Capacity: Invest in upskilling specialist nurses, pharmacists, and AHPs to support the model's multidisciplinary approach, ensuring sustainability and resilience.

2. Optimise Information Governance & Data Systems

1. Provide support to clinical teams in identifying & managing patients according to risk and treatment gap.
2. Providing intelligence to practices, clusters and HB/national level to identify gaps and impact from suboptimal care with targeted support to improve the reach to these areas.

Recommendation Expansion:

- Unified IG Framework: Develop a pan-Wales Information Governance framework that enables secure, real-time data sharing across primary, secondary, and community care settings.
- Interoperable Digital Infrastructure: Integrate existing platforms with ASCVD-specific dashboards to enable risk stratification, care coordination, and outcome tracking.
- Data-Driven Decision Support: Implement AI-enabled tools for identifying high-risk patients and prompting timely interventions, ensuring alignment with national digital health strategies.

3. Enhance GP Engagement Mechanisms

Recommendation Expansion:

- Formalised Collaboration Agreements: Establish Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) or Service Level Agreements

(SLAs) with GP clusters to define roles, responsibilities, and shared outcomes.

- Primary Care Champions: Identify and support clinical champions within primary care to drive adoption, provide peer support, and feedback into service design.

4. Strengthen Behavioural and Wellbeing Support

Recommendation Expansion:

- Integrated Wellbeing Pathways: Embed behavioural science-informed interventions (e.g., motivational interviewing, digital CBT) into routine care, with referral pathways to community wellbeing services.
- Social Prescribing Integration: Leverage social prescribing link workers to address non-clinical determinants of health such as isolation, physical inactivity, and financial stress.
- Routine Mental Health Screening: Incorporate validated tools (e.g., PHQ-9, GAD-7) into follow-up protocols to identify and manage co-morbid mental health conditions.

5. Refine Clinic Tools & Resources

Recommendation Expansion:

- Patient Empowerment Tools: Develop and distribute patient-held records, visual risk communication tools, and mobile apps that support self-monitoring and adherence.
- Point-of-Care (PoC) Testing Expansion: Scale the use of PoC lipid and HbA1c testing with embedded quality control protocols, reducing diagnostic delays and improving clinic efficiency.
- Digital Integration: Ensure tools are interoperable with national systems and support remote monitoring, particularly for rural or underserved populations.

6. Future Evaluation Design

Recommendation Expansion:

- Robust Evaluation Framework: Design a prospective evaluation framework using matched cohorts, stratified by risk level, geography, and socioeconomic status to assess impact.
- Mixed-Methods Approach: Combine quantitative outcomes (e.g., LDL-C reduction, hospital admissions) with qualitative insights (e.g., patient experience, staff feedback) to inform continuous improvement.
- Health Economic Modelling: Integrate cost-effectiveness and budget impact analyses into future evaluations to support business case development and policy advocacy.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Legislation and Policies for CVD prevention

Policies and legislation in Wales to promote healthy living and CVD prevention

The Wellbeing of Future Generations (Wales) 2015

The Wellbeing of Future Generations (Wales) 2015 set in law the need to consider the long-term strategic approach to deliver a better future. This was underpinned by 'A Healthier Wales', and which remains the vision and long-term plan for health and social care in Wales.

Heart Conditions Delivery Plan – 2017

This was produced by the Heart Conditions Implementation Group, published in January 2017. Prevention of cardiovascular disease was a major component of the plan, with multiple key actions developed with an aim to promote prevention of cardiovascular disease (CVD).

<https://www.gov.wales/sites/default/files/publications/2019-01/heart-conditions-delivery-plan-january-2017.pdf>

Public Health (Minimum Price for Alcohol) (Wales) Act 2018 helps reduce cardiovascular disease by making cheap, strong alcohol less affordable. By setting a minimum price per unit of alcohol, it discourages excessive drinking, especially among heavy drinkers. This can lead to lower rates of high blood pressure, heart attacks, and strokes, all of which are linked to alcohol misuse. The goal is to improve public health and reduce alcohol-related harm across Wales.

Healthy Weight: Healthy Wales Strategy launched in October 2019, supports cardiovascular health by aiming to reduce obesity—a major risk factor for heart disease and stroke. It promotes healthier eating, increased physical activity, and supportive environments to help people maintain a healthy weight. By tackling poor diet and inactivity, the strategy helps lower the risk of hypertension, high cholesterol, and other conditions that contribute to cardiovascular disease.

[North Wales Regional Partnership Board Annual Report](#)

A Healthier Wales – 2021

A Healthier Wales, published in 2021, was developed as a long-term health and social care strategy for Wales. The importance of prevention is key to this long-term strategy, as set out in the executive summary:

"This plan sets out a long-term future vision of a 'whole system approach to health and social care', which is focussed on health and wellbeing, and on preventing illness."

A Healthier Wales

<https://www.gov.wales/sites/default/files/publications/2021-09/a-healthier-wales-our-plan-for-health-and-social-care.pdf>

National Strategic Clinical Network for Cardiovascular Conditions

The National Strategic Clinical Network for Cardiovascular Conditions was established by the NHS Wales Executive (Executive, 2025), with three implementations networks sitting within the strategic clinical network, to support improvement, change (including innovation and value), delivery, and to address unwarranted variation in care. The National Implementation Networks consist of The National Cardiac Implementation Network, the National Vascular Implementation Network and the National Stroke Implementation Network, each of which has published a quality statement describing what good quality services should look like for each of the respective networks.

National Cardiac Implementation Network

National Clinical Lead: Dr Jonathan Goodfellow

The NCIN oversees a subgroup of 'cardiovascular disease prevention and awareness'.

The subgroup focuses on the prevention and early detection of cardiovascular disease and stroke and will consider measures addressing primary and secondary prevention.

The Quality Statement for Heart Conditions was first published in March 2021, and replaced the heart conditions delivery plan (2017). The statement summarises "what we are doing to improve care for people with heart conditions." It is stated that: "There also needs to be a focus on cross-working with other groups to address areas such as public health, prevention, rehabilitation, care for those who are critically ill or at end of life as well as collaboration with other conditions such as stroke, diabetes and vascular."

Quality Statement for Heart Conditions

<https://www.gov.wales/quality-statement-heart-conditions-html>

National Stroke Implementation Network

The Quality Statement for Stroke was first published in September 2021.

The quality statement describes what good quality stroke services should look like.

Prevention is stated as one of the quality attributes of the statement:

"Continued promotion of primary and secondary stroke prevention through the intervention of treatment and advice in line with current and evolving evidence base."

Quality Statement for Stroke

<https://www.gov.wales/quality-statement-stroke-html>

National Vascular Implementation Network

The Quality Statement for Vascular Disease was published in June 2023, as a response to the requirements set out in 'A Healthier Wales'.

The quality statement describes what good quality vascular services should look like.

Prevention is set out as one of the 23 quality attributes in the statement:

"High quality research should be undertaken into methods of preventing and treating vascular disease to aid the delivery of improved outcomes, identification optimum treatments and evaluation of new therapies."

Quality Statement for Vascular Disease

<https://www.gov.wales/quality-statement-vascular-disease-html>

The Environment (Air Quality and Soundscapes) (Wales) Act 2024 is expected to help reduce the burden of cardiovascular disease in Wales by addressing air pollution. The Act empowers the Welsh Government to set long-term air quality targets, implement low-emission zones, and enforce measures like anti-idling rules and smoke control to reduce harmful pollutants in the air.

Air pollution, especially fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂)—has been strongly linked to increased risks of heart attacks, strokes, and other cardiovascular conditions.

By improving air quality, the Act aims to lower exposure to these pollutants, thereby reducing the incidence and severity of cardiovascular diseases across the population. Additionally, the Act promotes active travel (like walking and cycling), which not only reduces emissions but also encourages physical activity, another key factor in preventing heart disease.

Public Health Wales Our Strategic Plan 2023 – 2026

Launched in March 2022.

PHW Strategic Plan 2023-2026

<https://publichealthwales.nhs.wales/about-us/board-and-executive-team/board-papers/board-meetings/2022-2023/30-march-2023/board-papers-30-march-2023/412a-board-20230330-strategic-plan-imtp-2023-2026/>

Public Health Wales Long Term Strategy 2023-2035

The PHW long-term strategy was published in May 2023, and sets out the vision for achieving a healthier future for Wales by 2035. The PHW strategy document set out six strategic priorities, one of which states:

Strategic Priority 4:

"Supporting the development of a sustainable health and care system focused on prevention and early intervention"

This is stated as a central priority for PHW, in supporting the health system to shift the balance towards prevention, early intervention and equity of care in order to improve outcomes for the population.

PHW Long-term Strategy:

<https://phw.nhs.wales/news/public-health-wales-vision-for-a-healthier-future-for-wales/working-together-for-a-healthier-wales/>

Food (Promotion and Placement) (Wales) Regulations 2025, is a new law aimed at tackling obesity and promoting healthier eating habits. This legislation will restrict the placement and price promotion of products high in fat, sugar, and salt (HFSS). It will ban multi-buy promotions such as "buy one get one free" for HFSS items and limit their visibility in key retail areas like store entrances, checkouts, and aisle ends, as well as on the homepages of online stores. While temporary price promotions and meal deals involving HFSS products won't be completely banned, they will be tightly regulated. The policy aligns with similar measures in England and is designed to reduce impulse purchases and encourage healthier choices across Wales.

Tobacco and Vapes Bill currently at the committee stage in the House of Lords includes provision for England and Wales and aims to reduce smoking and vaping, particularly among young people. A key measure is banning the sale of tobacco to anyone born on or after 1 January 2009, creating a "smoke-free generation." This is expected to significantly lower smoking rates over time.

Since smoking is a major risk factor for cardiovascular disease (CVD), the bill could lead to a substantial reduction in heart attacks, strokes, and related conditions. Additional restrictions on advertising, packaging, and public use of vapes and tobacco products will further support public health and reduce the burden of CVD on the healthcare system.

[Tobacco and Vapes Bill - Parliamentary Bills - UK Parliament](#)

Optimising treatment of cardiovascular disease risk factors (ABCD)

- Atrial fibrillation
 - o Stop a Stroke Quality Improvement Programme e.g. Stop a Stroke Campaign - Cardiff and Vale University Health Board).
- Blood pressure
 - o Size of The Prize is a modelling tool designed by UCL Partners and utilised across England to show how the NHS could prevent thousands of heart attacks and strokes by optimising the treatment of common risk factors like blood pressure and cholesterol. Data is being collated to develop a Size of the Prize for Wales.

- Cholesterol
 - o Familial Hypercholesterolemia (FH) Service Wales. FH is caused by an abnormal gene which results in very high cholesterol levels in the blood. People with Familial Hypercholesterolemia, if untreated, are at an increased risk of early coronary heart disease. The Familial Hypercholesterolemia Wales Service identifies and treats individuals and families in Wales.
- Diabetes
 - o The All Wales Diabetes Prevention Programme (AWDPP), led by Public Health Wales, offers targeted support to people who are at an increased risk of type 2 diabetes, with the aim of preventing them from developing this condition.
 - o Structured diabetes education programmes such as DESMOND.

Services supporting behavioural risk factors

- Healthy Weight Healthy You is a comprehensive strategy by Welsh Government aimed at preventing and reducing obesity. As part of this the Healthy Weight Healthy You programme offers personalised guidance to support individuals to manage their weight effectively. Health boards across Wales also offer services to support individuals to manage their weight.
- Help Me Quit was launched in 2017 and is a single brand for NHS stop smoking services in Wales. Help Me Quit is delivered by Public Health Wales and local health boards.
- The National Exercise Referral Scheme (NERS) is a Welsh Government funded health intervention incorporating physical activity and behavioural change techniques to support referred clients to make lifestyle changes to improve their health and wellbeing.
- Dan 24/7: Free bilingual helpline to support people with drug and alcohol dependence.

Appendix 2

Management Pathway for Blood Pressure and Lipid Lowering. Antihypertensive drug therapy, monitoring and treatment targets

Treatment of hypertension will be managed according to NICE guideline [NG 136]. Choice of antihypertensive drug, monitoring and treatment targets is provided below (fig1).

Lipid lowering therapy, monitoring and targets

Targets for low density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) and triglycerides (TG) will follow the 2019 European Society of Cardiology and European Atherosclerosis Society (ESC/EAS) guidelines for the management of dyslipidaemias. Target for TG level will be ≤ 1.7 mmol for all patients. LDL-C targets are presented (table 1).

Table 1. ESC/EAS 2019 recommendations for LDL-C

Recommendations	Class ^a	Level ^b
In secondary prevention for patients at very-high risk, ^c an LDL-C reduction of $\geq 50\%$ from baseline ^d and an LDL-C goal of < 1.4 mmol/L (< 55 mg/dL) are recommended. ^{33–35, 119, 120}	I	A
In primary prevention for individuals at very-high risk but without FH, ^c an LDL-C reduction of $\geq 50\%$ from baseline ^d and an LDL-C goal of < 1.4 mmol/L (< 55 mg/dL) are recommended. ^{34–36}	I	C
In primary prevention for individuals with FH at very-high risk, an LDL-C reduction of $\geq 50\%$ from baseline and an LDL-C goal of < 1.4 mmol/L (< 55 mg/dL) should be considered.	IIa	C
For patients with ASCVD who experience a second vascular event within 2 years (not necessarily of the same type as the first event) while taking maximally tolerated statin-based therapy, an LDL-C goal of < 1.0 mmol/L (< 40 mg/dL) may be considered. ^{119–120}	IIb	B
In patients at high risk, ^c an LDL-C reduction of $\geq 50\%$ from baseline ^d and an LDL-C goal of < 1.8 mmol/L (< 70 mg/dL) are recommended. ^{34–35}	I	A
In individuals at moderate risk, ^c an LDL-C goal of < 2.6 mmol/L (< 100 mg/dL) should be considered. ³⁴	IIa	A
In individuals at low risk, ^c an LDL-C goal of < 3.0 mmol/L (< 116 mg/dL) may be considered. ³⁶	IIb	A

ASCVD = atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease; FH = familial hypercholesterolaemia; LDL-C = low-density lipoprotein cholesterol.

^aClass of recommendation.

^bLevel of evidence.

^cFor definitions see Table 4.

^dThe term 'baseline' refers to the LDL-C level in a person not taking any LDL-C-lowering medication. In people who are taking LDL-C-lowering medication(s), the projected baseline (untreated) LDL-C levels should be estimated, based on the average LDL-C-lowering efficacy of the given medication or combination of medications.

The selection and prescribing of lipid lowering medications for the primary and secondary prevention of cardiovascular disease will follow NICE guidance and be in accordance with Swansea Bay and Hywel Dda University Health Boards' formulary guidance.

The following has been adapted from the NICE Clinical Knowledge Summary: Lipid Modification for CVD Prevention (July 2022) and provided as a guide to patient management:

The management of the lipid lowering therapy for the primary prevention of CVD risk will follow as:

- Offer lipid modification therapy to people aged 84 years and younger if their estimated 10-year risk of developing cardiovascular disease (CVD) using the [QRISK](#) assessment tool is 10% or more and lifestyle modification is ineffective or inappropriate.
 - Also, offer lipid modification therapy to people with type 2 diabetes who have a 10% or greater 10-year risk of developing CVD. For more information, see the CKS topic on [Diabetes - type 2](#).

- Consider offering lipid modification therapy (without the need for a formal risk assessment) to all people with type 1 diabetes.
- Offer lipid modification therapy (without the need for a formal risk assessment) to people with:
 - Type 1 diabetes who:
 - Are aged more than 40 years.
 - Have had diabetes for more than 10 years or have established nephropathy.
 - Have other CVD risk factors.
 - Chronic kidney disease.
 - Familial hypercholesterolaemia – patients with FH will be managed via the specialist FH clinics.
- Consider offering lipid modification therapy (without the need for a formal risk assessment) to people who aged 85 years or over (particularly people who smoke or have raised blood pressure), taking into account the risks and benefits of treatment, additional factors such as potential benefits from lifestyle modifications, informed patient preference, comorbidities, polypharmacy, general frailty and life expectancy.
- Offer high intensity statin treatment unless this is [contraindicated](#) (for example in pregnancy).
- Discuss the risks and benefits of statin treatment so that the person can make an informed choice about their treatment. Advise that:
 - High intensity statin treatment is the most clinically effective option for the prevention of cardiovascular disease (CVD). However, statins at any intensity reduce CVD risk compared with no treatment.
- If the person is willing to take a statin:
 - Prescribe atorvastatin 20 mg once a day.
 - Advise that:
 - Statin treatment should be adhered to, and should be combined with lifestyle measures (such as increase physical activity, reduce alcohol consumption, adopt a diet that helps reduce CVD risk).
 - [Follow up](#) the person to assess the effectiveness and tolerability of treatment.
- If statins are contraindicated, consider seeking specialist advice.
 - Do not routinely prescribe fibrates.
 - Do not offer bile acid sequestrants, nicotinic acid, omega-3 fatty acid compounds, or any of these (or a fibrate) in combination with a statin.
 - Do not offer coenzyme Q10 or vitamin D to increase adherence to statin treatment.
 - Consider treatment with ezetimibe for people with primary hypercholesterolaemia.
- If the person declines treatment with a statin, advise that their CVD risk should be reassessed again at a later date. Record their choice in their medical notes.

The management of the lipid lowering therapy for the secondary prevention of CVD risk will follow as:

- Offer high intensity statin treatment unless this is [contraindicated](#) (for example in pregnancy).
- Discuss the risks and benefits of statin treatment so that the person can make an informed choice about their treatment. Advise that:
 - High intensity statin treatment is the most clinically effective option for the prevention of CVD. However, statins at any [intensity](#) reduce CVD risk compared with no treatment.
- If the person is willing to take a statin:
 - Prescribe atorvastatin 80 mg once a day. Prescribe a lower dose if:
 - There are [drug interactions](#).

- There is an increased risk of [adverse events](#).
 - The person requests to start at a lower dose.
- o Advise that:
- Statin treatment should be adhered to, and should be combined with lifestyle measures (such as increase physical activity, reduce alcohol consumption, adopt a diet that helps reduce CVD risk).
 - Other drugs, some foods (for example, grapefruit juice) and some supplements may interfere with statins and to always consult the patient information leaflet, a pharmacist or prescriber for advice when starting other drugs or thinking about taking supplements.
 - The statin should be restarted if they stopped taking it because of drug interactions or when treating intercurrent illnesses.
 - They should seek medical advice if they develop [adverse effects](#) such as unexplained muscle symptoms (pain, tenderness, or weakness).
- o [Follow up](#) the person to assess the effectiveness and tolerability of treatment.
- If statins are contraindicated, consider seeking specialist advice (discuss with one of the lead Consultant Cardiologists).
 - o Do not routinely prescribe fibrates.
 - o Do not offer bile acid sequestrants, nicotinic acid, omega-3 fatty acid compounds, or any of these (or a fibrate) in combination with a statin.
 - o Do not offer coenzyme Q10 or vitamin D to increase adherence to statin treatment.
 - o Consider treatment with ezetimibe for people with primary hypercholesterolaemia who do not achieve target LDL-C.
 - o Secondary care treatment options may include proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 9 (PCSK9) inhibitor therapy for people with primary non-familial hypercholesterolaemia or mixed dyslipidaemia (after review by Consultant Cardiologist, see below)
 - If the person declines treatment with a statin, advise that their CVD risk should be reassessed again at a later date. Record their choice in their medical notes

Follow up after initiating statin therapy

- o If a greater than 40% reduction in LDL-C is not achieved:
 - Discuss adherence and timing of dose.
 - Optimise adherence to diet and lifestyle measures.
 - Consider increasing the dose of atorvastatin if started on less than 80 mg a day if the person is judged to be at higher risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD) because of comorbidities, risk score, or using clinical judgement.
- o If target reduction in LDL-C is still not achieved after appropriate dose titrations of atorvastatin, or because dose titration is limited by adverse effects:
 - Consider ezetimibe co-administered with atorvastatin for people with primary hypercholesterolaemia
- o Further treatment options (Consultant review) include a proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 9 (PCSK9) inhibitor, alone or in combination with a statin and/or other lipid-lowering drugs for people with primary non-familial hypercholesterolaemia or mixed dyslipidaemia at:
 - High risk of CVD – only if LDL-C level is persistently above 4.0 mmol/L.
 - Very high risk of CVD – only if LDL-C level is persistently above 3.5 mmol/L.

- **Recheck liver function tests (LFTs) within 3 months of starting treatment, and again at 12 months.** Further monitoring is not necessary unless clinically indicated (for example symptoms or signs of hepatotoxicity develop).
- **Routinely monitor for adverse effects of lipid modification therapy:**
 - o If unexplained muscle symptoms (such as pain, tenderness, or weakness) develop:
 - Check creatine kinase (CK) – do not measure creatine kinase levels in asymptomatic people.
 - Explore other possible causes of muscle pain or weakness and raised CK (if present) if they have previously tolerated statin therapy for more than 3 months.
 - Stop statin treatment if CK is five or more times the upper limit of normal.
 - Consider stopping treatment if muscular symptoms are severe and cause daily discomfort, even if the CK levels are not more than five times the upper limit of normal.
 - o If other adverse effects are reported when taking high-intensity statin treatment, discuss the following possible strategies with the person:
 - Stopping statin treatment and trying again when the symptoms have resolved to check if the symptoms are related to statin use, or
 - Reducing the dose within the same intensity group, or
 - Changing to a statin in a lower intensity group.
 - o Seek specialist advice about other possible treatment options if treatment is still not tolerated after three different statins have been tried for people at high risk of CVD, for example, people with chronic kidney disease, diabetes mellitus, or genetic dyslipidaemias. See the CKS topics on Chronic kidney disease, Diabetes - type 1, Diabetes - type 2, and Hypercholesterolaemia - familial for more information.
 - Consider treatment with ezetimibe for people with primary hypercholesterolaemia who have clinically significant adverse effects with statin treatment or who do not achieve ESC target LDL-C.
 - Secondary care treatment options may include PCSK9 inhibitor therapy for people with primary non-familial hypercholesterolaemia or mixed dyslipidaemia.
- For people taking ezetimibe monotherapy (if statins are contraindicated or not tolerated), consider ezetimibe with bempedoic acid if ezetimibe alone does not control low-density lipoprotein cholesterol well enough.

Appendix 3 EQ-5D (visit 1a and 12 months)

Under each heading, please tick the ONE box that best describes your health TODAY.

MOBILITY

- I have no problems in walking about
- I have slight problems in walking about
- I have moderate problems in walking about
- I have severe problems in walking about
- I am unable to walk about

SELF-CARE

- I have no problems washing or dressing myself
- I have slight problems washing or dressing myself
- I have moderate problems washing or dressing myself
- I have severe problems washing or dressing myself
- I am unable to wash or dress myself

USUAL ACTIVITIES (e.g. work, study, housework, family or leisure activities)

- I have no problems doing my usual activities
- I have slight problems doing my usual activities
- I have moderate problems doing my usual activities
- I have severe problems doing my usual activities
- I am unable to do my usual activities

PAIN / DISCOMFORT

- I have no pain or discomfort
- I have slight pain or discomfort
- I have moderate pain or discomfort
- I have severe pain or discomfort
- I have extreme pain or discomfort

ANXIETY / DEPRESSION

- I am not anxious or depressed
- I am slightly anxious or depressed
- I am moderately anxious or depressed
- I am severely anxious or depressed
- I am extremely anxious or depressed

- We would like to know how good or bad your health is TODAY.
- This scale is numbered from 0 to 100.
- 100 means the best health you can imagine
0 means the worst health you can imagine.
- Mark an X on the scale to indicate how your health is TODAY.
- Now, please write the number you marked on the scale in the box below.

YOUR HEALTH TODAY =

The best health you can image

The worst health you can image

Appendix 4: Questionnaire – general life style (Visit 1a)

1. Living arrangements	TICK the appropriate BOX
I live with partner / spouse /family / friend	
I live alone	
I live in a nursing home / other long term facility	

2. Have you been told by your doctor that you have any of these conditions?	TICK the appropriate BOX
Heart disease (angina, heart attack, heart failure or stroke)	
High blood pressure	
Problems from a stroke	
Leg pain when walking due to poor circulation	
Lung disease (i.e asthma, chronic bronchitis or emphysema)	
Diabetes	
Kidney Disease	
Disease of nervous system (i.e Parkinsons disease or multiple sclerosis)	
Liver Disease	
Cancer within the last 5 years	
Depression	
Arthritis	
None of the above	

3. Approximately how many units of alcohol do you drink on average per week?	TICK the appropriate BOX
Number of units (1 unit is a small glass of wine or half pint beer or small spirit measure)	UNITS

4. What level of exercise / activity did you mainly take LAST WEEK?	TICK the appropriate BOX
Light exercise (e.g walking slowly – housework or playing golf)	
Moderate exercise (e.g brisk walking, water aerobics, cycling on flat ground)	
Vigorous exercise (e.g jogging or running, swimming fast, cycling fast or up hills)	

More than 3 hours up to 4 hours	TICK the appropriate BOX
1 hour or less	
More than 2 hours up to 3 hours	
More than 3 hours up to 4 hours	
More than 4 hours up to 5 hours	
More than 5 hours up to 6 hours	
More than 6 hours up to 7 hours	
More than 7 hours	

6. Which of these describes your status?	TICK the appropriate BOX
Full-time employed or self-employed	
Part-time employed or self- employed part time	
Unemployed / seeking work	
Looking after home or family	
Student	
Retired	
Long term sick	
Disabled	

Appendix 5 (Final Visit)

Patient Experience Survey

The New Cardiovascular Management Clinic is a new service that aims to improve the management of your condition and improve communication between you and the [Insert health board] team responsible for your care. As part of the new service you will have access to healthcare professionals to help manage your condition and a digital platform to access to forms in which you can describe your symptoms and quality of life. This form is provided to all patients who have been through the new clinic and is used to help us assess its effectiveness and where we can improve. It should take between 10-20 minutes to complete/

For more information and to view [insert Health board] policies, please access the [Privacy notice](#) and [Your information, your rights](#).

Thank you for taking the time to complete this form.

Patient Survey

1 Are you completing this questionnaire for someone else?*

Yes

No

2 What is your relationship to the patient?*

Spouse/Partner

Parent/Guardian

Other family member

Friend

Social-care professional

Healthcare professional

Other

3 Why is your assistance needed? (Please select all that apply)*

The patient has a physical impairment that prevents them from completing the questionnaire

The patient has a mental impairment that prevents them from completing the questionnaire

The patient is under 16 years old

The patient does not speak English

Remote collection (e.g. telephone collection)

If you are helping someone to complete this questionnaire, please ensure that the information and opinions given are that of the patient and not your own.

Part A - Your Experience

4 Before you were referred to the Clinic, how many times did you see/speak to someone at your GP practice about your symptoms? *

Never

Once

Twice

3-5 times

6-10 times

I can't remember/don't know

5 When you saw the health care professional at the clinic, how easy was it to speak about your main concern? *

Very easy

Fairly easy

Neutral

Rather difficult

Very difficult

6 When the health professional was dealing with you, did they explain why you were referred to the Clinic & what being part of this clinic would involve? *

Yes, I had a full explanation

I had some explanation

I had no explanation

I can't remember/don't know

7 Were you provided with a physical, or online version of a patient information leaflet explaining what to expect when you attended the clinic?*

Yes

No

I can't remember / don't know

8 Were you given time to discuss any questions you had about the information in the patient information leaflet? *

Yes

No

I cant remember/ don't know

9 When thinking about the leaflet, how clear was the information included?*

It was easy to understand

It was a little confusing to understand

It was difficult to understand

I can't remember/didn't read it/wasn't given one

10 Is there anything else you would like to share about your experiences about your referral to the clinic?

Part B - Your Clinic Visits

11 During your pre-clinic invitation, did you have the opportunity to discuss your wellbeing or any other concerns that you may have had about your appointment?

Yes

No

I can't remember/I didn't have a pre-clinic phone call

12 During the pre-clinic invitation, were you able to speak in the language of your choice to fully understand what was being explained to you?

Yes

No

13 Were you made aware of how a friend/family member could support you through your experiences at the Clinic? *

Yes

No

I can't remember/don't know

14 When you arrived at the clinic, did a member of staff clearly explain what was going to happen during your appointment?

Yes, I had a full explanation

I had some explanation

I had no explanation

I can't remember/don't know

15 How did you feel about the time your appointments took to be completed?

It was about right

It was too long

It was too quick

I can't remember/don't know

16 Was attending the clinic convenient?

Yes

No

I can't remember/don't know

17 Were you able to wait in a suitable and safe environment?

Yes

No

I can't remember/don't know

18 Were your results or information provided to you explained in a clear way by the Clinic team? *

Yes, completely

Partly but I didn't fully understand

No, I did not understand

No, I was not given an explanation

I haven't had my results yet

I can't remember/don't know

19 As part of your visit, were you given clear information about what would happen next? *

Yes

No

I can't remember/don't know

20 What do you feel about the amount of information you were given about what would happen next? *

I received more information than I needed

I received about the right amount of information

I would have liked more information

21 Do you feel like you were listened during your visits to the clinic?

Yes, always

Yes, most of the time

Some of the time

No, not at all

I can't remember/don't know

22 Do you feel you were treated with dignity and compassion during your time under the Clinic's care?

Yes, always

Yes, most of the time

Some of the time

No, not at all

I can't remember/don't know

Part C - Your Overall Experience

23 I was happy with my overall care delivered by the clinic?

Agree

Disagree

I don't know

24 Is there anything you would like to tell us about your experience of the Clinic?

25 Is there anything that could have been done differently to improve your experience? *

26 Do you have the name and details of who to contact if you have any questions or need further information, following your appointment?

Yes

No

I can't remember/don't know

27 Did you experience any of these difficulties when travelling to appointments related to the Clinic? Please select all that apply. *

Length of travel time

Cost or access to suitable transport

Lack of information about finding the venue

Another transport related difficulty or accessibility issue

I had no difficulties

28 Is there anything else you'd like to tell us about your travel experience or ability to access the clinic? *

Thank you for completing this questionnaire. All your responses and comments will help to improve the Clinic experience for other patients.

TRITECH

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